

Abstract

Title of Dissertation:

**HOW ORGANIZATIONS LEVERAGE
COLLABORATIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR
KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT:
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

**Clark Shah-Nelson,
Doctor of Business Administration, 2020**

Organizations can lose knowledge as fast as they can create it. Retiring Baby Boomers, job-hopping Millennials and out-of-date communication and collaboration practices contribute to organizational knowledge loss. This knowledge loss costs organizations billions of dollars for re-learning and for hiring, onboarding and training new employees. Knowledge management strategies foster knowledge retention and are critical to facilitating innovation. Knowledge management can be enhanced using collaborative technologies such as enterprise wikis, instant messaging, collaborative writing, project management, blockchain and semantic web technologies powered by artificial intelligence. Through a systematic review and synthesis of 46 critically appraised studies that span global contexts and sectors, this dissertation informs

scholars and practitioners by providing evidence and recommendations to global organizations looking to implement, adopt or utilize collaborative technologies to retain knowledge, prevent knowledge loss or establish and strengthen an organizational culture that fosters knowledge management. Through thematic synthesis and qualitative analysis of inductive codes across scholarly articles, this research highlights aspects of affordances (access to knowledge, knowledge sharing across organizational boundaries, searchability) and organizational culture (knowledge sharing culture, transparency, the role of management) as keys to strategically leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management. Organizations can retain their knowledge and build innovative capacity by systematically adopting and implementing collaborative technologies. By fostering transparency and knowledge sharing across boundaries, encouraging managers and leaders to promote a collaborative and transparent culture, and prioritizing the continued use of these technologies, organizations can maximize their knowledge management outcomes.

Keywords: knowledge management, knowledge retention, collaborative technologies

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FOR KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT:
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

By

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University of Maryland Global Campus, in partial fulfillment
of the requirements for the degree of
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Preface

“An investment in knowledge always pays the best interest.”

— **Benjamin Franklin**

“Knowledge is a treasure, but practice is the key to it.”

— **Lao Tzu**

“The advancement and diffusion of knowledge is the only guardian of true liberty.”

— **James Madison**

“Share your knowledge. It is a way to achieve immortality.”

— **Dalai Lama XIV**

Dedication

I dedicate this dissertation to my father, Orin Lee Nelson, the first and primary administrator in my life. Through his work as a nursing home administrator and service as an elected town council member, he amply demonstrated how one can lead, support and care for an organization and a community. He passed away before I could finish this program and he could call me Doctor, but I know he would have been proud to see the fruition of this doctorate degree.

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Chapter 1: Introduction and Overview of the Management Problem

In the 2020 economy, knowledge is one of the most important forms of organizational capital. Knowledge needs to be managed and retained, or it may be lost at great cost to organizations. For many companies, knowledge is a key primary strategic asset and is critical for an organization to maintain a lasting competitive advantage (Bollinger & Smith, 2001; Gleason, 2019). Over the past few decades, intellectual capital has become many companies' most valuable asset (Carey, 2003; Sefidanoski, 2018; Stewart, 1994). Now, 75% of surveyed organizations state that creating and preserving knowledge is critical for their success (Namir & Edwards, 2020). This centrality highlights how important it is for organizations to retain and preserve their knowledge.

Organizational knowledge can exist in the form of intellectual property, patents, copyrights, explicit procedural everyday working knowledge of how to perform certain functions or duties, or tacit knowledge about the organization, such as who knows what. Imagine, for example, that in a day's time, half of the staff of an organization either quits, is laid off or goes on extended leave due to a global pandemic. A lack of documented tacit and/or explicit knowledge could severely affect the organization's ability to conduct its business. If an organization in this situation does not have evolved systems and processes in place for knowledge management (KM), knowledge sharing (KS) and knowledge retention (KR), it may experience knowledge loss (KL). Lesser and Prusak (2001) found that "when employees walk out the door, they take valuable organizational knowledge with them. But managers who think creatively can keep it in-house" (p. 101). Strategically managing knowledge makes it possible.

One of the primary ways that organizations store, retrieve, share, transfer, retain and manage knowledge is through the use of collaborative technologies (CTs). CTs allow

organizations to manage knowledge in ways that foster KR and prevent KL, preserving their valuable intellectual capital (Cerchione & Esposito, 2017). Many organizations have evolved new workplace cultures that elevate the urgency of KM. Conversations that once unfolded primarily via email, attachments and file servers now take place using digital collaboration tools, so rather than residing in databases, knowledge “flows dynamically across the digital communications channels that now define working relationships” (Deloitte, 2020, p. 65). This dissertation investigates this shift in how workers communicate and collaborate through a rigorous and transparent systematic review. It provides a roadmap showcasing how organizations leverage collaborative technologies for KM and retain valuable organizational knowledge.

Problem Statement

The impact of KL on an organization can be a serious threat. When employees leave an organization and their knowledge is not retained, the result is KL which can lead to loss of revenue. KL, also sometimes referred to as “brain drain” or “corporate amnesia” (Dahl-Jorgensen et al., 1999) costs organizations and companies billions of dollars. The financial burden of not sharing knowledge costs Fortune 500 companies an estimated \$31.5 billion a year (Myers, 2017; Nuclino, 2018). This burden includes the cost of personnel searches due to employee turnover, consultancy fees, onboarding and training (Growth Engineering, 2016) as well as the cost of wasted time, reduced creativity and reduced innovation (Poole & Sheehan, 2006). The departure of valuable employees imposes additional burdens on those left behind in the organization who may be compelled to compensate for the loss through extra work and responsibility. Remaining employees may suffer confusion and frustration due to lack of continuity and their inability to locate needed knowledge, lowering morale (Carey, 2003). To add to that, Massingham (2008) noted the impacts of KL on human, social, relational and structural

capital that in turn reduce organizational output, productivity, learning, memory and external knowledge flows. As a result, the costs associated with KL can be significant, with far-reaching impacts on an organization's bottom line and its ability to achieve its mission and vision. With so many detrimental impacts of KL, it behooves organizations to find effective ways to prevent it.

One of the oft cited factors related to KL is generational in nature. Baby Boomers, born between 1946 and 1964, started reaching the official retirement age of 65 years in 2011. By 2030, they will all be over 65, and over 10,000 will be retiring every day, each having an average of 35 years of work experience (Carey, 2003; Hanan & Stemke, 2014; Pew Research Center, 2010). Unless their work-related knowledge is captured and is accessible to their successors, it will be lost. To add to that loss, organizations sometimes pay exorbitant amounts to keep retirees on as consultants (Levy, 2011), doubling the cost of KL. In another generational trend, millennials have been found to hop from job-to-job twice as often as Baby Boomers while working more as freelancers in the gig economy (Nuclino, 2018). This requires onboarding and training that drive up the costs of staff turnover. Together, these generational changes can have a major effect on an organization's ability to retain its knowledge.

Outdated work practices can also result in the loss of knowledge in an organization, for example when knowledge is not properly shared. Many organizations still rely upon work methods and technologies that have not evolved since the 1990s, including heavy reliance on telephone conversations and face-to-face meetings that may lack proper documentation, and storage of created knowledge in email/attachments that are neither transparent nor easily transferable across employees (Somerville & Howard, 2010). Organizations that rely on these practices and technologies can suffer staggering KL when people leave the organization. Every time an office employee shares information in an email (rather than a more open project

management (PM) or instant messaging (IM) system) or creates and saves a document that exists only on their computer, the risk of loss of knowledge that could have been used by others in the same organization increases (Rashid et al., 2019). Due to these outdated work practices, many employees waste valuable time duplicating others' efforts trying to find information and figure out who knows what because they were not aware of other peoples' knowledge in the organization.

Potential Antidotes

A widely cited antidote to the problem of KL in scholarly literature is KS. Research has found that effective KS strategies can combat KL and enhance KR (Daghfous et al., 2013; Jackson, 2010; Reychav & Weisberg, 2009). KS also leads to increased creativity, innovation and performance (Gagné et al., 2019; Schneckenberg et al., 2015). As such, prioritizing KS is one way that organizations can prevent KL.

Collaborative technologies (CTs) include tools that multiple users can use either simultaneously or asynchronously to document, create, distribute, aggregate or share knowledge. In recent decades, CTs, which can enhance an organization's capacity to acquire, store, transfer, reuse, share and retain knowledge, have been deployed across many sectors (Hedgebeth, 2007). Several technologies have emerged since the first wave of the internet boom at the turn of the millennium. CTs include tools such as cloud-based file storage, sharing and collaborative writing (Google Drive, OneDrive, Dropbox), wikis (Atlassian Confluence), IM (Slack, Microsoft Teams), videoconferencing (Zoom, Webex), PM tools (like Atlassian Jira, Trello, Asana, Basecamp) and also include social media (SM) (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram), blogs and microblogs (Twitter, Reddit, Medium, etc.) (Leonardi & Neeley, 2017). Most recently, blockchain-based and Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered semantic web technologies have

enabled organizations to capture, share, update, distribute and retain knowledge. Such technologies also foster communication and collaboration and facilitate both global virtual teamwork and colocated office teamwork. These CTs enhance organizations' ability to manage knowledge.

Harnessing and leveraging organizational knowledge through KM practices and systems can produce positive outcomes. Whether the results are increased innovation, creativity or productivity, many organizations have implemented KM strategies to boost their efficiency (Sefidanosky, 2018) and help battle the costs of turnover (Massingham, 2018). How organizations manage this knowledge can have a significant effect on the organization's profitability, efficiency and longevity (Massingham, 2014). Organizations that do not actively create processes or a culture of KM or KS can lose knowledge as employees leave the organization, which can result in loss of revenue in searches, hiring, training, on-boarding and re-gaining the knowledge that was lost. KM systems and processes, by capturing, storing and transferring knowledge, have been a strategic area for organizations to leverage for competitive advantage. Figure 1 graphically displays the problems as well as the potential antidotes as described in the literature.

Figure 1*Graphic Representation of the Problem*

Note. The figure shows the problem of organizational knowledge loss and antecedents on the left, cited literature relating knowledge sharing to knowledge retention and linking collaborative technologies to knowledge sharing on the right.

While there is academic literature reporting on various aspects of these collaborative tools and technologies, many studies are specific to a particular tool and context. Furthermore, studies often point to a particular benefit of a specific technology. This dissertation aims to focus on a broader swath of organizational contexts, geographies, tools and technologies to identify how organizations have leveraged a wide range of CTs for KM.

Purpose of the Study and The Research Question

The purpose of this dissertation is to inform scholars and practitioners by providing a systematic review of the evidence and recommendations to global organizations looking to implement, adopt or utilize collaborative technologies to retain knowledge, prevent knowledge loss or establish and strengthen an organizational culture that fosters knowledge management.

By examining evidence from a myriad of global contexts, this dissertation aims to uncover the ways in which organizations adopt, implement and utilize CTs to manage their knowledge. It intends to pinpoint how organizations benefit from deploying these CTs for KM systems and the common factors that influence decision-making, cultural shifts and successful change management. Ultimately, the goal of this dissertation is to inform both scholars and practitioners of the ways CTs can be implemented and the organizational benefits that can be realized through KM with CTs.

Significance for Management

KL is a significant concern for management. Organizations are losing knowledge and need to retain it. When knowledge is lost and not retained it can affect innovation, productivity, morale and turnover. As such, the costs associated with KL can be staggering. Thus, management teams need to implement KM systems or processes strategically, harnessing the best available evidence to support decision-making.

Throughout the employee life cycle, from hiring to on-boarding to meetings to appraisal, managers significantly influence employees' practices and the overall organizational culture. As central stakeholders and influencers of organizational culture, managers play a significant role in retaining knowledge. While responsibility for KM falls primarily on an organization's leadership, managers largely oversee what, how, how much, how often, and to what degree employees record, transmit, retrieve and store knowledge. Managers shape how organizations implement and adopt technologies.

CTs can foster (organizational) retention of both tacit and explicit knowledge and are therefore important to study in depth. Over the past two decades, as CTs have become more ubiquitous within and across organizations, they have evolved in usability and functionality.

Now, CTs provide a foundation for KM systems for organizations. Research provides evidence of successful (and not so successful) implementation of CTs across varying organizational contexts. Therefore, strategies for implementation and utilization of CTs are useful to organizations and management.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this dissertation is limited to an organizational context and may be biased toward literature published in the most recent decade (2010-2020). Although an exhaustive search was conducted, it is possible that not every study with an organizational context and collaborative technology for knowledge management focus was captured. While attempts were made to include the latest cutting-edge technologies, published academic literature may lag industrial advances, so new technologies may not be represented.

The Research Question

While there is much academic literature that explores various aspects and dimensions of CTs, typically the studies cover one context and/or one technology. The aim of this dissertation is to discover, by examining a broad swath of studies, contexts and CTs, how various practices, tools and strategies best lend themselves to effective KM. What are the mechanisms by which these CTs affect organizational outcomes? What are the most important or effective KM practices for organizations to implement? How are leaders and managers successfully building KM capacity and retaining knowledge through the use of CTs? How are CTs being implemented, supported, and managed?

Based on this line of inquiry, this study utilizes the context, interventions, mechanisms, outcomes (CIMO) logic to define the research question. Context is defined as the geography, culture, sector, or level of study (individual, organizational or a specific group or population).

Interventions are the variables that are typically being administered in studies. Mechanisms help explain the relationship between the intervention and the outcome. The outcome is the effect of the intervention on the population or context (Briner et al., 2009). By identifying these components, researchers are able to define what they are seeking to answer from the research.

Table 1 displays the resulting CIMO-logic that was used to develop the research question:

Table 1

CIMO for Research Question

Context	organizations
Intervention	collaborative technologies
Mechanisms	(the objective of this research question is to identify these)
Outcome	knowledge management

Based on this CIMO framework and the goals of this study, the research question framed to guide this study is: *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* This research question was the cornerstone of all aspects of this dissertation that follow: the scoping literature review, research methodology, findings and recommendations to scholars and practitioners.

Definitions and Terminology

The following defines several key terms used in this dissertation.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): Computer software that can turn structured or unstructured data into usable knowledge by detecting patterns, developing rules and analyzing business data from many inputs to help solve problems (Paschen et al., 2019).

Blockchain: Distributed ledger technology (DLT) which distributes transactions over a peer-to-peer network. Bitcoin is an example of currency, which is stored and distributed via blockchain. (Ilbiz & Durst, 2019).

Collaborative Storage/Writing: Technology tools that support individuals or groups collaborating on writing and maintaining documents, most often on cloud-based servers.

Explicit Knowledge: Knowledge that specifies how to accomplish certain tasks, which can be articulated and can be communicated to others (Nonaka & von Krogh, 2009).

Instant Messaging (IM): A technology for sending messages, links, images, or media that can be one-to-one or one-to-many.

Knowledge base: A record of stored knowledge that could be in the form of a repository of documents, a wiki or other combinations of media for storage and retrieval (Paschen et al., 2019).

Knowledge loss (KL): The result of employees (at all levels of tenure) leaving an organization without having recorded or stored their knowledge (Liebowitz, 2008).

Knowledge management (KM): Continuous process and/or systematic means of collecting, creating, storing, transferring and sharing knowledge, typically through the use of technology tools.

Knowledge retention (KR): A critical component of knowledge management (Levallet & Chan, 2019) organizational knowledge and expertise is retained through technology, mentoring and storytelling (Losey, 2002).

Knowledge sharing (KS): Sharing of knowledge, where the goal may be to create new knowledge through recombination or to utilize existing knowledge (Krumova & Milanezi, 2014).

Knowledge transfer: The transfer of knowledge from person to person and/or to machines that is enabled through knowledge sharing.

Organizational knowledge: Individual knowledge that is on a continuum between tacit and explicit, and which is amplified and made available to an organization's knowledge system (Nonaka & von Krogh, 2009).

Semantic Web: A layer or extension of the World Wide Web (WWW) in which semantics are defined, which makes it possible for both humans and machines to better parse the content (Tyagi et al., 2015).

Tacit knowledge: Non-codified knowledge that largely exists in the minds of employees, such as who knows what (Cary, 2003) and which may incorporate personal values, emotions and experiences (Brătianu, 2019).

Wiki: A collaborative web site or collection of web pages that allows easy knowledge capture, editing, updating and sharing (Liebowitz, 2008) and which allows collaborative co-authoring (Tyagi et al., 2015).

Chapter Summary

In summary, this chapter introduced the background, problem, purpose, scope and research question that is driving this dissertation. Since knowledge is a key asset for organizations, if not the most important asset, an organizations' capacity to capture and retain knowledge when employees depart has significant financial consequences. Collaborative technologies contribute to an organizations' ability to capture, share, retain, reuse and ultimately manage knowledge. While individual studies have documented how some organizations have

implemented and/or utilized a particular collaborative technology to help manage knowledge, this dissertation casts a wide net to explore organizational strategies for implementing, utilizing and fostering collaborative technology use for knowledge management.

Organization of the Dissertation

This dissertation is the result of a systematic review and academic study of literature to examine the research question. Chapter 2 provides a scoping literature review and theoretical framework; Chapter 3 a detailed description of the methodologies utilized; Chapter 4 a thorough analysis and description of findings; and Chapter 5 conclusions and implications for management.

Chapter 2: Scoping Literature Review and Theoretical Frame

This chapter provides a scoping review of the literature and describes the theoretical frame that informs this dissertation and its research question: *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* This dissertation utilizes a systematic review of the literature to answer this question. A systematic review is a way of “synthesizing research in a systematic, transparent, and reproducible manner with the twin aims of enhancing the knowledge base and informing policymaking and practice” (Tranfield et al., 2003, p. 207). The purpose of this systematic review is to inform scholars and practitioners through an analytic and thematic synthesis of the best available evidence to answer the research question. The aim is to provide evidence-based recommendations on collaborative technologies (CTs) that help organizations retain knowledge, prevent knowledge loss (KL), and establish and strengthen an organizational culture that fosters knowledge management (KM).

The Literature Landscape

This section contextualizes the research question by reviewing previous scholarship about its primary constructs and by providing an overview of relevant research in related fields. To that end, this section describes relevant prior research findings related to dimensions of knowledge, CTs, and affordances and elaborates on the theoretical underpinnings that inform this dissertation and which point to the gaps in research that this study addresses.

Data Versus Information Versus Knowledge

It is important to differentiate between data, information and knowledge. Data are facts and figures that are not organized (Hajric, 2018). Data can be transformed into information by providing meaning, which adds value (Davenport & Prusak, 2000). Information is data that are contextualized, calculated, categorized and condensed (Hajric, 2018). Organizational knowledge

is “a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information” (Davenport & Prusak, 2000, p. 5) and represents value added to information in the form of know-how, insight, experience and understanding (Hajric, 2018). Thus, organizational knowledge is an epistemological mix of subjective and objective experience as it is captured, shared and converted (Nonaka et al., 2006). Due to the more advanced state of knowledge in relation to data and information, in terms of context and value, the focus of this research is on organizational knowledge.

Dimensions of Knowledge: Theoretical Underpinnings

As the business world adapts to a knowledge-based society, there has been an accompanying recognition that organizations can create new knowledge and that their ability to do so can greatly affect their success. According to Nonaka’s (1994) seminal theory of organizational knowledge creation, this knowledge is created through continuous interplay of tacit and explicit knowledge, spiraling through four modes of knowledge conversion: socialization, externalization, combination, and internalization (SECI). The theory posits that organizational knowledge is created through this continuous (and endless) cycle of knowledge conversion through these four modes (Nonaka, 1994) (see Figure 2). This knowledge creation cycle helps organizations overcome “the individual boundaries and constraints imposed by information and past learning by acquiring a new context, a new view of the world and new knowledge” (Nonaka et al., 2006, p. 1182), which helps organizations adapt as the environment changes. The nature of this adaptation can mark the difference between success and failure (Nonaka et al., 2006). Thus, the sharing and contextualization of information leads to the

conversion and creation of organizational knowledge, which helps organizations continuously adapt, innovate and succeed.

There are several important aspects of knowledge that shape the current state of the literature as it relates to this dissertation and its research question. The following are some of the primary constructs that are discussed in the next sub-sections: tacit and explicit knowledge, KL, knowledge retention (KR), knowledge sharing (KS), knowledge hoarding and knowledge management (KM) as an overall umbrella.

Figure 2

Organizational Knowledge Creation and SECI

Note. Adapted from “Turning Mirrors Into Windows: Knowledge Transfer Among Indigenous Healers in Limpopo Province of South Africa,” by J.R. Maluleka and M. Ngoepe, 2018, *South African Journal of Information Management*, 20, p. 2. CC BY.

Tacit versus Explicit Knowledge. To better understand knowledge creation, it is important to differentiate between tacit and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge is that which is unarticulated, and which relates to experiences, intuition and senses (Nonaka et al., 1996), such as the knowledge of who to approach for answers to a particular problem or question. It is typically not documented and resides in peoples’ minds. Explicit knowledge is typically in print or spoken out loud, such as documentation of how to complete a set of processes. As the continuum of knowledge from tacit to explicit is converted through the four SECI modes, organizational knowledge is created. (Nonaka & von Krogh, 2009). *Socialization* relates to tacit knowledge sharing. *Externalization* is the articulation of tacit knowledge as it moves toward explicit concepts. *Combination* is the blending of explicit knowledge and *internalization* is the individual conversion of explicit knowledge to tacit (Nonaka et al., 2006). This spiral cycle describes how the continuum of organizational knowledge is continuously captured and converted.

Knowledge Loss. KL is an organizational issue that has taken on greater importance in recent years. Generational churn has been leading Baby Boomers to retirement (Carey, 2003; Hanan & Stemke, 2014; Pew Research Center, 2010), and Millennials are more rapidly changing jobs than in the past (Nuclino, 2018). In addition to losing “what they know” - organizations also stand to lose “who they know” and other tacit knowledge (Parise et al., 2006). Further, Levallet and Chan (2019) highlight two types of KL, including failure to capture organizational knowledge and failure to maintain stored knowledge. Some researchers differentiate between

intentional and unintentional KL, in which organizations intend to “unlearn” knowledge that is not useful (Daghfous et al., 2013). This study focused on unintentional organizational KL - employees leaving the organization without retaining the knowledge they have created.

Documented consequences of KL indicate a number of negative effects on organizations. Lin et al. (2016) reported results of KL finding reduction of performance, absorptive capacity, competitiveness, organizational output, productivity, memory and learning. Further, they found an increased cost of training and risk of losing competitive advantage (p. 1759). This finding was reinforced in a longitudinal study by Massingham (2018) which found that the negative impacts of KL included loss of productivity (morale), capability gaps and resource cuts. In addition, Carmel et al. (2013) mentioned that the firm’s credibility in the eyes of the client can suffer and revenue may decrease. Thus, KL is a form of capital loss (Lin et al., 2016) that can significantly impact organizations. These negative consequences highlight the urgency of preventing KL.

Evidence suggests a number of effective strategies for mitigating KL. Intergenerational learning (IGL), through activities such as mentoring, convening research teams, and conducting workshops and training programs (Bratianu & Leon, 2015), as well as identifying and capturing knowledge of expert older workers (Carmel et al., 2013) have been found to be successful. Shankar et al. (2013) highlighted the need for proper planning, communication and identification of vital knowledge to be codified. Jennex (2014) proposed a systematic instrument for assessing risk factors of knowledge loss, creating an inventory of knowledge, assessing criticality and developing retention plans. Ultimately, to prevent KL, organizations must implement mechanisms for KR (Lin et al., 2016). Many researchers have found that some mitigation of KL can be achieved through strategic self-study, identification of critical knowledge and purposeful retention of identified expert knowledge.

Knowledge Retention. KR is a vital antidote to KL. KR is critical for organizations to maintain sustainable performance and competitive advantage (Doan et al., 2011; Gleason, 2019). KR can be strategically planned and implemented by organizations to prevent KL starting with identifying critical knowledge that is at risk of loss (Liebowitz, 2008). KR strategies have evolved in recent decades. Early KR strategies included the mainly non-technical use of group storytelling forums for sharing successes and failures, online newsletters, printed publications and mentoring between retirees and younger workers (Losey, 2002). Three primary stages of successful KR define the scope: prioritizing, documenting and integrating knowledge back into the organization (Levy, 2011). In an empirical study, Martins and Meyer (2012) focused on organizational and behavioral factors that influence KR, including individual knowledge behaviors such as acceptance of team goals, constructive conflict solving and willingness to determine the types of knowledge that most need to be retained. Recently, research attention has turned toward technologies to manage knowledge. Lin et al. (2016) found empirical evidence that technology tools can mitigate KL by helping retain critical knowledge. KR strategies to retain intellectual capital have evolved from largely offline and analog methods to predominantly online and digital methods. Rashid et al. (2019) posit that organizational KR strategies can advance innovation, growth, efficiency and competitive advantage. These findings highlight the value of strategic implementation of processes and tools that foster KR for organizational success.

Knowledge Sharing. KS is an important component of retaining and managing organizational knowledge. KS includes the sharing, transfer or exchange of knowledge between colleagues (Suhindra et al., 2017), the sharing of task-related expertise to help others (Ahmad & Karim, 2019) and the creation of new knowledge (Razmerita et al., 2016). KS methods can be

categorized at the individual, team and organizational level and analyzed using a knowledge-based view of the firm (KBV) (Ahmad & Karim, 2019; Suhindra et al., 2017), social capital theory and the context of communities of practice (Wang & Noe, 2010). Researchers have also linked KR with knowledge sharing (KS). For example, Rashid et al. (2019) held that KR is dependent upon KS practices of codification and personalization. Fostering KS within an organization is one of the ways to successfully retain its knowledge.

KS depends upon the behavior and attitudes of individuals in an organization. Successful KS behavior among virtual teams is related to individual positive attitudes of trust, reciprocal benefits (Killingsworth et al., 2016), enjoyment of helping others (Revang & Olaisen, 2019), monetary rewards, support, modeling and recognition from management (Razmerita et al., 2016). Barriers to KS include lack of trust, time and technology constraints (Rosen et al., 2007); resistance to change and knowledge hoarding (Razmerita et al., 2016); and free riders (those who benefit from KS but do not contribute) (Dyer & Nobeoka, 2000). Additionally, employees may feel as if talking to others is good enough as a form of KS or they may perceive a lack of personal gain (Massingham, 2014). Scholars caution that posting information without any restrictions can result in an “information junkyard” (Revang & Olaisen, 2019, p. 877). Therefore, it is important for organizations to provide individuals with an environment, structure and systems that support the behaviors and attitudes that facilitate and strengthen KS practices.

There are several noted benefits to organizations that prioritize the sharing of knowledge. These benefits include increased innovation and organizational competitiveness (Wang & Noe, 2010), as well as cost reductions, time savings, lower costs for coordination and shorter development cycles (Ahmad & Karim, 2019; Massingham, 2014). KS is fundamental to success in KM initiatives (Wang & Noe, 2010) and is one of the most important organizational operation

activities. With these benefits in mind, organizations must systematically promote and sustain KS activities.

KS practices cut across various work paradigms, such as telework, colocation (working in the same building), and communities of practice (COPs). Whereas some researchers questioned the value of technology for KS beyond increasing the breadth (Alavi & Leidner, 2001), others found that KS can thrive through the use of online technologies and does not require offline or colocated interaction (Olaisen & Revang, 2017). One popular form of KS is in COPs, which are ad hoc groups of people who communicate, share and grow in knowledge through a common interest in a particular topic (Babajani-Vafsi et al., 2019; Brätianu, 2019; Liebowitz, 2008).

KS is an important behavior under the umbrella of KM literature. As part of a KM system (Paroutis & Saleh, 2009), KS plays an essential role for innovation in organizations (Areed et al., 2020). Due to the interconnectedness of KS and KM, scholars have at times written about them almost interchangeably, for example by discussing KS at length within a paper with KM in the title or vice versa (Massingham, 2014). KS is perhaps one of the most important aspects of strategic KM systems and practices, and it is only enhanced and made easier through CTs.

Knowledge Hoarding. Knowledge hoarding is a challenge for KM and KS. When employees gather, create and/or collect knowledge without sharing it, it is known as knowledge hoarding (KH) (Babajani-Vafsi et al., 2019) or knowledge entropy (Brätianu, 2019). Hoarded knowledge is of little value (Alavi & Leidner, 2001). Some employees may hoard because they believe it will create job security (remain valuable, lessen the risk of being replaced) or they don't want to appear to try to "suck up" to management (Razmerita et al., 2016, p. 1237). Others hoard due to jealousy or competitiveness with colleagues (Babajani-Vafsi et al., 2019). Organizations who wish to foster KS need to address KH.

Some interventions were found to decrease the probability of KH behavior. These include increasing the perception of efficacy, enhancing group identification feelings and increasing the perceived pay-off (Cabrera & Cabrera, 2002). KH can also be converted to KS (Razmerita et al., 2016). While Alavi and Leidner (2001) claim that KH cannot be reduced through technology, they acknowledge that a cultural shift can foster such a change. The shift from hoarding to sharing can also be accomplished by amplifying the employees' perception that others depend upon them and helping them see the value of sharing rather than putting pressure on them to do so (Gagné et al., 2019). Change toward KS can also be achieved through the creation of COPs or virtual COPs. COPs should avoid competitiveness (Babajani-Vafsi et al., 2019) and excessive interference from top management, as these can hinder KS (Schofield et al., 2018). By addressing KH, organizations can foster an environment that is better for KS.

Knowledge Management. KM is a broad umbrella that can have differing definitions for various organizations. KM can be broadly defined as a combination of people, technology and processes (Al Mansoori et al., 2021) that capture, store, share, use and change individual knowledge into organizational knowledge (Lee, 2001) or as a system that manages organizational knowledge entropy (Brătianu, 2019) and creates value out of intangible assets (Liebowitz, 2001). At its core, KM is about people in organizations harnessing, capturing, storing, sharing and transferring their intellectual capital. This can be accomplished through various means, both analog and digital, colocated and distributed, with and without technology. Given major advances in personal computers and web and cloud-based technology, KM is typically entwined with modern technologies. Nevertheless, Al Mansoori et al. (2021) found that the human factor is the predominant component (70%) of KM, followed by processes (20%) and technology (10%). Regardless of how KM is defined, the underlying principle is that critical

knowledge is captured and stored so that it can be shared, retrieved and transferred across organizations.

The field of KM has undergone significant change and evolution since its origins in the 1980s. In particular, the advance of personal computers and spread of email into offices across the world in the 1990s helped usher in a period of theoretical and practical growth. As organizations moved away from warehousing knowledge toward a more networked approach, KM underwent a paradigm shift (Paroutis & Saleh, 2009). With an increased emphasis on organizational knowledge creation in “an emerging knowledge society” in which Information Technology (IT) played a major role (Nonaka et al., 1996), scholars continued to find ways that the flexible capabilities of IT could support and extend KM initiatives to create, store, transfer and apply knowledge in organizations (Alavi & Leidner, 2001). However, researchers also noted several challenges to the use of IT in KM including ineffective practices for storage and retrieval, duplication, weak access and transfer across organizational silos that are dependent upon the overarching KM strategy (Venkitachalam & Ambrosini, 2017). Yet, scholars continue to find that new forms of collaborative technologies such as crowdsourcing, wikis, cloud computing and collaborative filtering can increase the impact of KM initiatives (Cerchione & Esposito, 2017) as well as decrease the need for colocation and drive innovation (Olaisen & Revang, 2017). As KM has evolved, and through the addition of collaborative technologies, KM has moved toward being an enterprise solution, one that is strategic at the organizational level, not just among individuals or small groups.

Collaborative Technologies

Technologies such as email, spreadsheets, documents and file sharing servers first made a major impact on some industries in the 1980s (for early adopters) and most in the 1990s

(mainstream). Such technologies moved companies from paper-oriented systems or massive mainframe computer storage to networked personal computers. The advent of the World Wide Web (WWW) in the early 1990s brought with it a maelstrom of invention, with waves of Web 2.0 technologies that were more collaborative and cloud-based starting in the late 1990s (Wahi et al., 2016). These Web 2.0 collaborative technologies enabled networked people such as employees and students and teachers to work together on creating, updating, maintaining, and sharing documents, multimedia and other forms of stored knowledge and information. Many organizations adopted not only email and networking capabilities, but also CTs such as wikis (a set of simple, easily editable web pages that individuals or groups can share and maintain), instant messaging (IM), project management systems, file sharing and collaborative writing or graphics applications, videoconferencing and social media applications. As organizations adopted these technologies across their entire enterprise, they became known as “Enterprise 2.0” (Wahi et al., 2016). CTs have made an impact on the evolution and change to KM systems and practices.

In the past decade, collaborative and social technologies have been on the rise. Over 70% of companies report using them in a recent survey of 4200 companies (Leonardi & Neeley, 2017). Many large corporations have moved from large and unwieldy KM systems to using various Web 2.0 collaborative and/or social technologies (Grace, 2009). Whereas scholars in 2009 were stating that “very little is known about factors leading to success or failure” of online collaborative technologies (Paroutis & Saleh, 2009), they have since been found to enhance knowledge sharing (Anders, 2016) which can foster knowledge retention in the organization. However, there is significant variability in terms of the kind of technologies in use, their adoption and implementation, the prevalence of their use, and their effect on organizational

culture. There is a gap in the literature relating to the mechanisms through which CTs bring value to organizations (Ajjan et al., 2012). This study aims to delve further into the mechanisms by which CTs are leveraged by organizations for KM.

On the individual level, collaboration intensifies interaction, increasing the probability that knowledge residing in one individual's mind will be expressed to others. Trust, interest and participation are necessary to make CTs effective for KS (Levy, 2009). Collaboration brings organization members together to solve problems and to work on projects. (Droege & Hoobler, 2003). Through collaboration, employees have the opportunity to observe and experience the applications of others' tacit knowledge. Collaboration provides the employee interaction necessary to diffuse tacit knowledge.

Some of the primary tools that have been used for KM include knowledge bases, wikis, IM, social media, collaborative storage/writing tools, AI and semantic web technologies.

Knowledge base. A knowledge base is a primary KM artifact. A knowledge base can be non-technical in nature (Levallet & Chan, 2019; Nonaka, 1994), but for the purposes of this study, it refers to a common repository that houses organizational knowledge. This repository could be a shared networked drive of documents, internet cloud-based file sharing site, wiki, IM system or a combination of a number of different tools that work together to store, share and retain knowledge (Arndt et al., 2019; Levallet & Chan, 2019; Sathik & Venkat, 2015). No matter where the knowledge base resides, this provides the organization a centralized location for its knowledge.

Wikis. Wikis such as Wikipedia.org are web pages that can be easily edited without users needing to know web Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML). The term “wiki” derives from the Hawaiian word for “fast” or “quick,” underlining the ease and speed of adding and editing wiki

pages to collaboratively share knowledge (Kapp, 2007). Wikis first appeared in 1994 (Levy, 2009) and can function as an easy to use central repository that can save organizations time and money (Grace, 2009). Wikis are helpful for codification and centralization of accessible organizational knowledge for distributed team members (Zahedi et al., 2016). Wikis provide an easy way for organizations to document their knowledge.

Wikis have been researched extensively and have proven to be valuable for knowledge management. Empirical studies have found a positive correlation between wiki use and knowledge sharing intention (Wang & Wei, 2010). They have also found that wikis can foster collaboration, KS and organizational culture change (Pedraza-Nafziger, 2018), and that they are key to KM due to their collaborative nature (Grace, 2009). A number of researchers have studied how wikis are implemented. While many attempts have failed (Khuzaimah et al., 2015), there are organizational factors such as people, technology, business process and environment/work context that can contribute to successful implementation (Alqahtani, 2017b). Wikis can also be extended using semantic web technology, which make the structure of the wiki contents accessible to machines and AI applications on the web through annotations and ontologies for enhanced searching and connectivity (Schaffert, 2006). Wikis have proven to be a lasting and important CT for KM in organizations.

Instant Messaging (IM). While many people know IM primarily for its one-to-one, text-based communication that dates back to the 1990s and AOL Instant Messenger, this technology has evolved to provide much more in terms of connectivity and knowledge sharing. More recent applications in the IM realm include Slack and Microsoft Teams, both of which allow organizations to share knowledge at the group/team/enterprise level and use multimedia content with interoperability with many other systems. IM crosses organizational boundaries to enable

informal learning through group, topic or project-based “channels,” and improves ease of search and the possibility of codification, compared to telephone conversations (Kapp, 2007). In previous decades, many expressed doubts over whether IM was part of Enterprise 2.0 (Levy, 2009) in which organizations started moving toward cloud-based systems for email and other technologies so that all employees could authenticate with a single sign-on. More recently, researchers have found IM to be part of the “enterprise social networks” that help information flow seamlessly across organizations (Revang & Olaisen, 2019, p.877) and which can play an important role in creating, sharing and retaining knowledge (Ajjan et al., 2014). Not surprisingly, Enterprise Instant Messaging (EIM) has grown in popularity. While adoption and usage of IM/EIM typically lags email, IM/EIM has played an increasingly important role across organizations over the past decade.

Collaborative Storage/Writing. While wikis offer organizations a space for collaborative writing and knowledge storage, other technologies also appear in the literature. Google Docs (Google Drive), SharePoint, and similar tools offer collaborative writing and editing and provide a knowledge repository to store documentation, designs and policies (Levy, 2009; Pedraza-Nafziger, 2018). One of the key functions of these tools is that they typically allow users to see in real-time what others are editing, typing and deleting, creating live collaborative and interactive spaces.

Artificial Intelligence and the Semantic Web. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has increasingly played a role in KM. AI encompasses various software capabilities or “computational agents” that solve problems based on “what it knows” (Paschen et al., 2019, p. 1411). AI can help convert unstructured data to structured data and ultimately to knowledge (Paschen et al., 2019) through the process of data mining, ontologies, mapping and codification

(Liebowitz, 2001). Although researchers as recently as 2018 have noted that AI has not lived up to expectations (Hajric, 2018), research and development continues and matures. Recently, Al Mansoori et al. (2021) found in a systematic review of a decade of AI literature that AI helped managers make decisions based on complex sets of data through data mining and warehousing, and that “recent advancements made in Artificial Intelligence play a vital role in knowledge management at modern organizations, as they foster processes and facilitate tasks” (p. 177). While AI continues to play an increasing role in KM, 67% of surveyed companies have yet to incorporate it into their KM strategies (Namir & Edwards, 2020). Thus, AI can be considered an emerging technology that companies on the cutting edge are deploying for their KM systems.

The semantic web and related technologies are also known as “Web 3.0,” a term that refers to structured content and knowledge models that use ontologies, AI, annotation, tagging and other metadata to support knowledge storage and retrieval. As mentioned above, researchers have noted semantic wikis for the enhancements they provide for knowledge management. Further semantic web technologies are noted for their ability to conflate and synchronize distributed sets of data in support of distributed collaboration (Arndt et al., 2019). They also can provide “human–robot teams heterogeneous knowledge bases, which increases the shared awareness in teams to correctly perform tasks and understand each other by grounding high-level knowledge into low-level information and vice versa” (Yasdani et al., 2019). The semantic web is powered by and interwoven with AI and will play an increasingly important role in the next decade.

Affordances

The construct of affordances plays a role in understanding implementation and usage of collaborative technologies. The definition of affordances has evolved since its origin relating to

animals' perception about what a tool might allow them to do (Gibson, 1986; Strong et al., 2014). Markus and Silver (2008) brought the concept into the internet age by defining "functional affordances" as:

"a type of relationship between a technical object and a specified user (or user group) that identifies what the user may be able to do with the object, given the user's capabilities and goals. More formally, functional affordances are defined as the possibilities for goal-oriented action afforded to specified user groups by technical objects." (p. 622)

Thus, affordances related to technology have been defined as the potential of goal-oriented behavior and concrete actions as a result of using technology in practice and in a specific context. Affordances are also the product of the relationship between an IT artifact and actors in an organization (Strong et al., 2014). In other words, a technology tool may be used in a certain context and in a specific way to accomplish a goal, but this may vary according to the context (Bobsin et al., 2019; Gal et al., 2014). Two organizations could use a tool such as IM in very different ways, with different resulting affordances of that use. IM could afford one organization with the ability to remotely track conversations, while another might rely on it for sharing resources. Most recently, Leonardi (2017) proposed that social media affordances can help overcome barriers to KS in large organizations when they are used for normal everyday communications that "leak" knowledge (p. 57). The reasons why companies adopt certain technology tools relate to the expected affordances, and the benefits these tools bring to organizations are related to the ways people use them and the affordances they offer to the organization and its culture. This dissertation will explore what the literature corpus reveals about collaborative technologies and the ways they afford organizations to better manage their knowledge.

Literature Interpretive Model/Conceptual Model

Based on the review of the literature relating to ways organizations can prevent knowledge loss and foster knowledge retention, this dissertation builds on the conceptual model proposed by Levallet and Chan (2016) (see Figure 3). Whereas their model focuses entirely on knowledge loss and retention, this dissertation specifically examines how collaborative technologies are used by organizations to foster knowledge management, which can lead to competitive advantage and innovation capacity.

Figure 3

Conceptual Map of Factors Related to the Research Question

Note. Strategies and methods of preventing knowledge loss and fostering knowledge retention for knowledge management. Adapted from “Knowledge Loss and Retention: The Paradoxical Role of IT,” by N. Levallet and Y. E. Chan, 2016, *Successes and Failures of Knowledge Management*, (p. 240). Copyright 2016 by Elsevier, Inc.

Narrative of Conceptual Model Relationships

The conceptual model in Figure 3 shows the relationship between organizational knowledge loss and retention, using collaborative technologies that foster knowledge sharing, reuse, transfer, acquisition, storage and retrieval. The conceptual model also depicts how organizations lose stored knowledge when it is not maintained through continued retrieval and/or reuse (Levallet & Chan, 2019). The model also builds on Levallet and Chan's (2016) model by including some of the documented outcomes for organizations that retain and manage their knowledge, including competitive advantage (Ilbiz & Durst, 2019) and innovation capacity (Ali et al., 2020). The conceptual model highlights the central role collaborative technologies can play in knowledge management, but leaves open the question as to the mechanisms by which they do so.

Thesis Statement

Collaborative technologies can be strategically adopted, implemented and deployed for organizational knowledge management. This dissertation, through a systematic review of the literature, will provide empirical evidence of the mechanisms, practices and ways that organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management.

Chapter Summary

This chapter provided the historical and theoretical context and record of scholarship related to the research question. The chapter highlighted the current state of the central constructs of this study by exploring the differences between data, information and knowledge, dimensions of knowledge, collaborative technologies and working theories related to knowledge management in learning organizations. Ultimately, this chapter highlighted the academic historical context surrounding the research question and, by highlighting research gaps, provided

the foundation for conducting a systematic review of the literature related to answering the research question. The next chapter will describe the methodology undertaken to implement the systematic review of the best available evidence to answer the research question.

Chapter 3: Method

This chapter describes the methodology employed to answer the research question: *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* The purpose is to shed light on the mechanisms by which organizations utilize collaborative technologies to retain knowledge. This dissertation is the product of an evidence-based research framework. It utilizes evidence-based management principles and processes to locate the best available evidence to inform the research question. This chapter defines and describes these terms, conveys the research design and elements, explains why this methodology is utilized and describes how it informs the research question through its rigorous and transparent process.

Review Design and Methodology

Evidence-Based Management

Organizational managers and leaders are often forced, due to either lack of time or other resources, to make decisions based on intuition, rather than evidence. Evidence-based management (EBMgt) can help bridge this gap by providing managers and leadership with aggregated evidence to help inform decision-making (Briner et al., 2009). Due to its overarching goal of informing the research question for practitioners, this dissertation utilizes an EBMgt approach to research. Briner et al. (2009) define EBMgt as such:

“EBMgt is about making decisions through the conscientious, explicit, and judicious use of four sources of information: practitioner expertise and judgment, evidence from the local context, a critical evaluation of the best available research evidence, and the perspectives of those people who might be affected by the decision.” (p. 19)

Principles of EBMgt help translate research evidence into practices and recommendations that solve organizational problems (Rousseau, 2006). Through rigorous and transparent processes, EBMgt provides organizations the ability to support or negate the intuition of managers and leaders with data. While it is important to acknowledge that not all managerial opinions are

incorrect (Chalmers, 2003), using EBMgt helps practitioners base their decisions on empirical evidence of effectiveness (Pfeffer & Sutton, 2006). By utilizing the principles and practices of EBMgt, this dissertation synthesizes a heterogeneous collection of evidence to inform the research question.

EBMgt is not a new concept in the field of management and business administration. It is an adaptation of evidence-based medicine for the field of management (Gubbins & Rousseau, 2015), which grew out of evidence-based approaches in medical science and healthcare from the 1980s (Tranfield et al., 2003). Both evidence-based medicine and EBMgt emphasize the importance of empirical evidence or “best evidence” (Gubbins & Rousseau, 2015) which can be qualitative, quantitative or theoretical (Briner et al., 2009). Gubbins and Rousseau (2015) proposed an evidence hierarchy based on research design, in which meta-analysis is at the top (more causality, least bias), followed by randomized control trials (RCTs), non-randomized control studies, longitudinal studies, cross-sectional/survey designs, case studies and, at the bottom, expert opinions (least causality, most bias). Yetley et al. (2017) later included systematic reviews of RCTs at the top of the hierarchy and edited a few categories. Figure 4 highlights the evidence hierarchy, showing higher and lower levels of evidence quality and risk of bias across differing types of studies.

Figure 4*Evidence Hierarchy*

Note. Adapted from “Options for Basing Dietary Reference Intakes (DRIs) on Chronic Disease Endpoints: Report From a Joint US-/Canadian-Sponsored Working Group” by E. A. Yetley, A. J. MacFarlane, L. S. Greene-Finestone, C. Garza, J. D. Ard, S. A. Atkinson, D. M. Bier, A. L. Carriquiry, W. R. Harlan, D. Hattis, J. C. King, D. Krewski, D. L. O’Connor, R. L. Prentice, J. V. Rodricks, and G. A. Wells, 2017, *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 105, p. 259S. Copyright 2017 by American Society for Nutrition.

EBMgt has continued to evolve into a family of scientific approaches to problem-solving and decision-making that are explicit, mindful and systematic (Briner et al., 2009, p. 22). The evolution and maturation of the scientific approaches of EBMgt make it a fit for this study.

Not all researchers agree on the effectiveness of EBMgt. Morrell and Learmonth (2015) argued that EBMgt is narrow and inflexible in its definition of evidence, and that it is too

positivistic. Their concerns can be addressed through pluralism, critical reflexivity and a broader definition of evidence. Gough et al. (2012), on the other hand, found that the systematic review method can be successfully applied to many kinds and variations of research types and questions. This dissertation addresses these concerns of inflexibility by using a broad definition of acceptable evidence and its critical reflexivity.

The EBMgt approach was utilized for this dissertation due to its appropriateness for scientifically and empirically collecting evidence to help answer the research question. One of the fundamental cornerstones of EBMgt practice is systematic review (Briner et al., 2009). This study brings together the four essential elements of EBMgt through the process of a systematic review and thematic synthesis of the best available evidence to answer the research question.

Systematic Review

A systematic review, as defined by Harden and Thomas (2005), is comprised of a seven stage process: defining a research question; developing a review protocol; conducting a comprehensive search for research evidence; applying inclusion/exclusion criteria; conducting a quality assessment of the included evidence; extracting data and synthesizing findings. This can be compacted into five steps, per Gough et al. (2012) and as seen in Figure 5. Because they are transparent and comprehensive, systematic reviews provide a rigorous method for researching, analyzing and synthesizing evidence (Dixon-Woods, et al., 2005; Thomas & Harden, 2008) that is clear, explicit and accountable (Gough et al., 2012). While systematic reviews do not necessarily provide “answers,” they provide information about what is known and unknown about a particular question (Briner et al., 2008). Systematic reviews allow researchers to gather, appraise, and analyze evidence in order to answer a research question.

Figure 5*Five Steps of a Systematic Review*

By surveying findings from similar studies, systematic reviews bring individual studies out of isolation to better inform policy and practice (Chalmers, 2003) and manage accumulation of knowledge (Harden & Thomas, 2005). For practitioners, systematic reviews also provide a qualitative means of informing practice without searching, locating and processing all the individual studies (Thomas & Harden, 2008). Qualitative research is appropriate for answering questions of how and/or why particular interventions work (or not) (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006; Snilstveit et al., 2012), which aligns with the goals of this study. Systematic reviews, like meta analyses, reside at the top of the hierarchy of evidence (Gubbins & Rousseau, 2015). As a rigorous and transparent research methodology, systematic review is an appropriate approach for this dissertation.

Thematic Synthesis

One of the aims of this systematic review is to inform practice through the analysis of primary literature. A cornerstone of this analysis is a synthesis of findings from studies that meet the inclusion criteria. In this context, synthesis is defined as a method of transforming the findings of individual primary studies “in order to build a 'connected whole'” (Gough et al., 2012, p.180). In other words, the researcher analyzes the content of the findings from included articles; notes commonalities and conceptual linkages; and weaves them together into a new aggregated whole, which exceeds the disconnected parts in its ability to more comprehensively answer the research question. This process allows the researcher to systematically, rigorously and transparently provide recommendations based on an exhaustive review of existing literature.

While there are several different types of synthesis, this dissertation focused on thematic synthesis. Dixon-Woods et al. (2005) presented thematic analysis as a process of identifying recurring and prominent themes in order to create a summary of common themes. Thomas and Harden (2008) further defined thematic synthesis as “a tried and tested method that preserves an explicit and transparent link between conclusions and the text of primary studies; as such it preserves principles that have traditionally been important to systematic reviewing” (para. 4). Coding is a process of content analysis that helps define and extract key concepts from the findings of both quantitative and qualitative research (Snilstveit et al., 2012; Thomas & Harden, 2008). The three steps in thematic synthesis include coding the findings, defining descriptive themes among the codes, and combining to generate analytical themes (Gough et al., 2012; Snilstveit et al., 2012; Thomas & Harden, 2008). By doing so, thematic synthesis is known to produce results and findings that are relevant to practice and policy (Booth et al., 2018; Thomas & Harden, 2008). Thematic synthesis was therefore deemed suitable for this study.

Two primary types of reviews include aggregative and configurative. Reviews may contain aspects of one or the other or fall somewhere on a continuum with aspects of both (Gough et al., 2012; Snilstveit et al., 2012). Aggregative reviews lean toward testing pre-defined concepts while configurative reviews are more exploratory (Gough et al., 2012). With its aim to explore patterns that emerge from the literature itself, this dissertation employs a configurative thematic synthesis of the findings.

Review Initiation

The systematic review grew out of a need to help solve the organizational problem of knowledge loss, while examining how collaborative technologies influence organizational knowledge management. After defining the overarching research question based on the context, intervention and outcomes, methods of systematic review and thematic synthesis were employed.

Identification of Journals and Databases

The researcher conducted searches using the University of Maryland Global Campus library “Journal Finder” in order to locate journals which published articles related to “collaborative technologies” and/or “organizational knowledge.” In addition, the researcher identified a list of databases based on best fit to answer the research question that included Business Source Complete, Computer Science OneFile, Computers & Applied Sciences Complete, Emerald Insight, ABI/Inform, and Dissertations and Theses Global (ProQuest).

Search Strategy

The strategy employed for this systematic review aimed to uncover the best available evidence to answer the research question. To accomplish this, the researcher conducted comprehensive database searches along with targeted broad searches and consulted with academic and industry experts in the field of knowledge management.

Search Terms

Thomas and Harden (2008) argue that achieving conceptual saturation and a heterogenous set of studies are appropriate for qualitative research studies such as this one. The researcher began by conducting searches with terms such as “knowledge loss” and “knowledge retention” combined with “collaborative technology” in order to pinpoint easy-to-locate resources. With the help of the University librarian for doctoral studies, the researcher conducted searches of the University library OneSearch database (which includes 57 databases) and the ProQuest database.

Table 2

Synonym Terms and Search Keywords

Key Terms	<i>Collaborative Technology</i>	<i>Knowledge</i>	<i>Organization</i>
Synonym Terms	collaborative software groupware instant messaging chat videoconferencing wikis	retention sharing transfer management storage	organizations corporations business company community of practice

Based on the search terms identified from the literature and researcher’s experience, the following search string was composed with the assistance of the doctoral librarian and queried in the ProQuest databases:

noft(organization OR corporat* OR business* OR compan* OR "communit* of practice") AND noft("collaborat* technolog*" OR "collaborat* software" OR groupware OR "instant messag*" OR "live chat*" OR "online chat*" OR videoconferenc* OR wiki* OR slack OR jira OR sharepoint OR "microsoft teams" OR "google hangout*") AND*

noft(knowledge NEAR/3 (retention OR retain OR shar* OR transfer* OR manag* OR stor*)) AND stype.exact("Conference Papers & Proceedings" OR "Trade Journals" OR "Reports" OR "Books" OR "Working Papers" OR "Scholarly Journals" OR "Dissertations & Theses")*

A similar but slightly different string was utilized in the UMGC OneSearch database:

(organi?ation OR corporat* OR business* OR compan* OR "communit* of practice") AND ("collaborat* technolog*" OR "collaborat* software" OR groupware OR "instant messag*" OR "live chat*" OR "online chat*" OR videoconferenc* OR wiki* OR slack OR jira OR sharepoint OR "microsoft teams" OR "google hangout*") AND (knowledge n3 (retention OR retain* OR shar* OR transfer* OR manag* OR stor*)).*

This search identified 1054 articles. In addition, based on consultation with a Subject Matter Expert in the field of Knowledge Management, additional searches were conducted to locate articles from the past year and for terms that were not included in the original search string but which could uncover articles about emerging collaborative technologies in knowledge management, such as artificial intelligence, text mining, blockchain and machine learning. Queries were made in OneSearch using the following search terms: *"knowledge management" AND "instant messaging"; "knowledge management" AND "artificial intelligence"; "knowledge management" AND "social media"; "artificial intelligence" collaboration tools; and "knowledge management" AND blockchain.* Each of these searches were limited to terms within the titles of articles published in 2019 and 2020. The articles located were reviewed and screened similarly to the other batches. The resulting 59 additional articles were added to the identified records for screening, as shown in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Moher et al., 2009) diagram in Figure 6. The PRISMA is a commonly used diagram

illustrating how articles are identified, screened, reviewed and moved to exclusion or inclusion in the systematic review, and provides accountability and transparency for this research.

Figure 6

PRISMA Diagram of Article Search and Screening Process

The researcher conducted the search and further limited the results using built-in library database limiters as appropriate. For example, rather than searching for terms in “all text” the researcher limited the results to the abstract field, with the understanding that this would focus the search to articles in which the search terms were of central importance as opposed to those that mentioned the search terms incidentally or in passing. The researcher further limited the search to articles published in the English language and removed books, magazines, news and commentary from the retrieval criteria. Further searches were conducted in specific journals, in white papers, and in grey literature to ensure that all the best available information was available for the analysis. With a focus on scholarly literature with rigorous and transparent

methodologies, the search strategy was also limited to the publication dates of 2010-2020. The reason for this range is due to the changes in technology and culture that occurred in this timeframe with the explosion of social media and other technologies. While collaborative technologies were used by organizations before this time period, the focus of this study is on more recent collaborative technologies, including those that have become ubiquitous in the last decade or so, including wikis, instant messaging, document sharing/collaborative writing, blockchain, artificial intelligence-powered search and semantic web. Articles that addressed the research question, which did not duplicate already existing findings and which expanded the coverage of this systematic review were included in the body of evidence.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

After searching, locating, retrieving and downloading the search results, 1113 records were exported and loaded into Zotero and Covidence software for title and abstract screening as seen in Figure 6. The process of importing these studies into Covidence removed 297 duplicates, leaving 816 articles to be screened. Each article title and abstract were reviewed to confirm that the study met the criteria for inclusion for this systematic review. Inclusion criteria were defined as follows:

Inclusion:

- Articles that discussed collaborative technology use in organizations
- Knowledge management, knowledge retention, knowledge sharing and collaborative technology were key constructs
- Written in English
- Published between the years 2010-2020
- Qualitative, quantitative and mixed-method studies

Exclusion:

- Purely education-oriented or school-oriented
- No mention of benefits to organization
- Lack of collaborative technologies
- Focused on one particular tool/technology without consideration of implementation/strategy/mechanisms relating to knowledge retention/management
- Primary focus on e-learning/training
- Written in languages other than English
- Individual level only

A total of 662 of the 816 articles did not meet the inclusion criteria and were excluded from full text screening. Since titles and abstracts often do not always provide a complete picture of the contents of each article, the researcher conducted a full text screen of the remaining 154 articles to further assess whether each included findings that addressed the research question. The exclusion criteria included wrong outcomes, study design, intervention, unavailable, duplicative, wrong setting, or does not significantly contribute to answering the research question. This review further limited the studies to 46 that were appraised for quality and relevance to the dissertation.

Quality Appraisal

Sufficiency and relevance to the research question are key to quality. Assessing the overall quality of articles ensured that the evidence they provided is sufficient (Gough, 2007). This allowed the researcher to identify the studies' relevance the research question (Gough, 2007). Thus, a rigorous process of appraising the articles included in the study was conducted.

There are several frameworks commonly used in systematic reviews for the purpose of appraisal. Weight of Evidence (WoE) is a framework that is “a useful heuristic for considering how to make separate judgements on different generic and review-specific criteria and then to combine them to make an overall judgement of what a study contributes to answering a review question” (Gough, 2007, p. 223). The WoE was used to assess the integrity and coherence of evidence, how appropriate the form of the evidence is, and the ability of the evidence to answer the research question (Gough, 2007). These three key assessments are then weighted and combined to provide an overall score for each study. Another common framework that conforms with the WoE assessment is known as TAPUPAS, which assesses seven dimensions of the evidence: transparency, accuracy, purposivity, utility, propriety, accessibility and specificity (Pawson et al., 2003). These frameworks were utilized to assess study quality.

Method of Quality Appraisal of the Included Studies

The researcher utilized the TAPUPAS and WoE frameworks for assessing the quality and applicability of each included study. To facilitate this, Covidence software was employed to score, document and tabulate the overall qualities, notes and scores for the criteria of transparency, accuracy, purposivity, utility, propriety, accessibility and specificity. Each area was assessed a numeric score for high (3), medium (2) or low (1) qualities of the research as seen in Appendix A. The overall average score was then tallied for each study, providing a relative measure to inform the researcher of the quality and appropriateness of the research articles for answering the research question. Using descriptive statistics, studies that had an overall average score above the median were noted as “high level” while those below the median were noted as “low level.” This provided information to the researcher regarding the relative quality and

overall weight of each article in terms of its findings in this study. Categorizing articles as high or low quality also allowed for their differentiation through coding analysis, as discussed below.

Descriptive Coding

In qualitative research, coding is the process of creating a word or phrase that symbolically captures the essence of a piece of data or evidence and is part of the analysis of the data (Saldaña, 2009). It is a process of reducing the data in order to better understand it and render it into reportable units (Elliott, 2018). By coding the findings of the included articles, the researcher reduces the data into a smaller, more manageable set that is easier to analyze. Coding also allows the researcher to more easily pinpoint commonality, differentiation, themes, categories and trends across multiple articles. By doing so, the researcher is able to develop descriptive themes that are closely related to the primary articles and can also develop analytical themes that generate new interpretations, explanations or constructs (Thomas & Harden, 2008). As such, the 46 included articles were all coded to extract their essence.

The process utilized for this study included coding using both Hypothes.is annotation software and Atlas.TI software. Article findings were initially coded in Hypothes.is by highlighting passages and assigning codes as tags. This was done in Hypothes.is due to the ease of being able to do so as each article was being read and assessed, and with the understanding that this would facilitate the later analysis using Atlas.TI. Each passage that was coded was assigned as many tags as necessary to capture the essence of the finding, and to note which collaborative technology and/or dimension of knowledge was being discussed. The codes were also entered using Atlas.TI, due to the advanced capability for analysis and structuring of the codes that this software allows.

Subject Matter Experts

The researcher consulted with a Subject Matter Expert (SME), Dr. Jay Liebowitz, PhD, a scholar in the area of knowledge management who has authored several books on the topics of business intelligence and knowledge management, sharing, and retention. Over several meetings, Dr. Liebowitz provided feedback on the article selection, recommended additional journals and topics to explore and contributed to the overall research strategy and process. Included articles were shared with Dr. Liebowitz at key intervals, and he provided feedback regarding the corpus as well as ideas for further resources and exploration. Based on feedback from Dr. Liebowitz, several small searches were added later in the article screening process to include cutting edge terminology to locate appropriate studies that covered some of these topics.

Analysis and Synthesis Methodology

Method of Synthesis

Synthesis is the process of taking multiple inputs and weaving them together into a new whole. Once the codes were all entered, they were analyzed for commonality, and in some cases codes deemed to have the same fundamental meaning were grouped together. Groups of codes that were similar in nature were then identified. Examples of code groups include: organizational outcomes, culture, collaborative technology functionalities, affordances, adoption/implementation, and leadership/management. Once in groups, the researcher was able to identify the most common code groups and assess the key themes and categories of the data.

The code groups were further analyzed by looking at the number of articles that contain the various codes (as opposed to the total number of times a particular code was used). For example, one article might have been coded with “searchability” nine times, whereas another might have been coded with “searchability” three times. By assessing the number of articles

coded with the term at least once, the researcher was able to pinpoint which codes were most common (see Appendix C). Codes were then assigned colors according to their prevalence, with the codes with the highest prevalence assigned the color green; those in the middle, orange; and the least common, red. Document groups were created in order to differentiate “high” quality articles (those above the median from the quality appraisal) vs. “low” quality articles (below the median). Such differentiation allowed the researcher to visually see at a glance the codes, and then code groups, that had the most (and least) commonality across included articles and to see differences between the quality groupings. Further code groups were then created for the green “top” codes and groups, in order to facilitate more data analysis of the groups and codes and to see where the co-occurrence of codes was present. The researcher then utilized various analytical functionality in Atlas.TI to view networks, co-occurrence and frequency of codes, code groups, and document groups. Examples of these can be seen in Appendix C.

Using these analytical processes and techniques, the researcher then created findings from the top themes and categories revealed from the coding and data analysis across all 46 included article findings. These are presented in Chapter 4.

Chapter Summary

This chapter described the methodology utilized by the researcher to answer the research question. It portrayed the search strategy, selection process, appraisal, descriptive statistics, coding, and analysis methods. By utilizing the described methodology of systematic review, the researcher adhered to and employed practices supported by prior research as noted and cited in this chapter. Employing systematic review as the primary process for locating the best available evidence to generate new knowledge, this evidence-based research study used a rigorous search strategy, screening regimen, quality appraisal, inductive thematic coding and analysis to

synthesize the findings of the evidence. The findings that resulted from this methodology are presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 4: Analysis and Findings

The purpose of this dissertation was to provide evidence and recommendations to organizations looking to utilize collaborative technologies (CTs) to retain knowledge, prevent knowledge loss (KL) or establish or strengthen knowledge management (KM) by answering the research question: *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* This research aimed to uncover trends and commonalities that may inform organizations to help them prevent KL and foster knowledge retention (KR). To that end, this systematic review was conducted following the rigorous methodology described in the previous chapter to locate the best available evidence to answer the research question. This chapter describes the overall analysis and findings that resulted from the systematic review of the evidence.

Description of the Data Set

Following the methods described in Chapter 3, this study resulted in the inclusion of 46 articles to answer the research question. The PRISMA diagram in Appendix A shows the progression the researcher made from the initial searches to the final dataset, which is a combination of 39 academic peer-reviewed journal articles, 4 conference proceedings, 2 dissertations and 1 working paper. The 46 articles include a mix of 23 empirical studies, 8 theoretical papers, 13 case studies, 1 action research, and 1 general report as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7*Types of Articles Included in the Systematic Review*

Included articles cover global organizational contexts, industries and sectors, providing a varied and diverse data set with which to explore the evidence to answer the research question. The included studies originate from every continent (see Figure 8) and across sectors that include healthcare, software development, financial service, media, manufacturing, nursing homes, supply chain businesses, retail, marketing, energy and design. As such, this dataset represents a broad swath of business and organizational sectors. See Appendix B Table B1 for a full listing of the included articles and the descriptive statistics across articles.

Figure 8

Countries Included in the Systematic Review

The range of years within which the articles were published is from 2010-2020, and representation within each year can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9*Published Years of Included Articles*

The studies discussed the utilization of a range of collaborative technologies that included wikis (17), web 2.0 (11), IM (6), social media (6), AI (3), SharePoint (2) and blockchain (1) as seen in Figure 10. A display of the corresponding study dates can be found in Appendix A, Table 2A.

Figure 10*Count of Primary Collaborative Technology***Results of the Quality Appraisal of the Data Set**

Included studies were read and assessed based on a combined TAPUPAS and WoE scoring rubric as described in Chapter 3. The final 46 studies included in the systematic review were all deemed to be of high enough quality to have at least some value in answering the research question. The results of the quality appraisal can be viewed in Appendix A.

Results of the Synthesis of the Articles in the Data Set

The researcher inductively coded and performed thematic synthesis on the 46 included studies to answer the research question. The results of this coding were analyzed based on the frequency of codes across all articles. Codes were grouped based on common themes and categories as they related to one another, and the results of this final synthesis point to two

primary categories that help answer the research question: affordances and organizational culture.

Affordances

As defined in Chapter 2, affordances exist in the gray area between what the technology does or is capable of, and how the people in the organization actually use it. Affordances are the result of the interplay of these two factors. It is entirely possible that two different organizations use the same collaborative tool in different ways, resulting in a different set of affordances for each organization. However, after examining the data coded across the 46 included articles, this study found that four affordance attributes rise to the top for organizational knowledge management: searchability, finding useful information/locating experts, access to knowledge, and crossing organizational boundaries.

Searchability. Beyond access, knowledge workers must be able to find the information they need, when they need it. Searchability was one of the most commonly coded affordances, discussed by 17 of the 46 (37%) of the included articles. While search is a key functionality that has existed within software at various levels for decades, this study explored several notable dimensions of searchability and related affordances across collaborative technologies that produce a number of benefits to organizations, including enhanced efficiency (Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016; Bibbo et al., 2012; Khumalo & Mearns, 2019), performance (Bolisani & Scarso, 2016; Choy et al., 2018; Durao & Dolog, 2014; Ngoma, 2013; Ou et al., 2010), innovation (Krumova & Milanezi, 2014; Paschen et al., 2019; Schneckenberg et al., 2015) and social engagement (Anders, 2016; Dal Mas et al., 2018; Skok et al., 2013; Teo et al., 2011). As an example of how searchability provides efficiency, Bibbo et al. 2012 found that “the wiki eliminated countless unnecessary meetings, conference calls, mass emails, and it redirected

employees with basic questions to a ready resource for answers, the wiki has dramatically increased the efficiency of our unit” (p. 25). Thus, a number of organizational benefits were noted as a result of searchability, and this was an important finding.

Searchability was found to be useful for problem solving and several other aspects in organizations. Hemsley and Mason (2013) defined employee search as “searching for information to exploit in concrete ways, to take action or to make a decision, to create new information” or to solve a problem (p. 154). The facilitation of problem-solving was an oft coded affordance that searchability facilitates, whether through collaboration and social presence (Archer-Brown & Kietzmann, 2018; Durao & Dolog, 2014; Evans et al., 2015; Krumova & Milanezi, 2014; Pimmer et al., 2018; Schneckenberg et al., 2015), facilitating self-sufficiency (Baek, 2012; Menolli et al., 2015), just-in-time answers (Hemsley & Mason, 2013), or in general (Jarrahi & Sawyer, 2013; Stocker et al., 2012). The importance of searchability highlights the need for organizations to ensure that their knowledge is captured in ways that afford searchability. Searchability aspects as discussed in the review are largely categorized in two primary groups: technology-related and human-related.

Finding Useful Information: Technology-Related. Having knowledge collected in a unified system such as a wiki, knowledgebase, project management or IM system enables workers to search by keyword, phrase, tag, etc. to access a repository of shared explicit knowledge (Schneckenberg et al., 2015; Teo et al., 2011), operational procedures (Khumalo & Mearns, 2019), experiences from dispersed projects (Breunig, 2016) and observations about the current status of the enterprise (Stocker et al., 2012). But having all this information and knowledge readily available can also lead to information overload, which can be overwhelming (Anders, 2016). Thus, while the technology can facilitate searching and finding answers, there is

also evidence of further need to organize knowledge in ways that structure it to facilitate locating it.

Several technological contrivances, including meta-search, meta data, semantic wikis, tagging, annotation, structuring, recommenders, ontologies and folksonomies were noted by authors regarding the optimization of searchability for organizations. Some of these are increasingly automated, such as with Artificial Intelligence (AI), and others require humans to interact with the knowledge, to shape, tag or structure it. Intelligent search, meta-search and/or unified search, which aggregates searches across multiple databases and/or applications into a single list were noted for facilitating the retrieval of knowledge (Schneckenberg et al., 2015; Tyagi & Yang, 2015). Semantic wikis allow users to annotate and add metadata, to tag concepts, contexts or other attributes according to an ontology (Zapp et al., 2013, p. 448). Whereas an ontology is more formal, explicit and structured, folksonomies are more organic, as they are constructed by a user community (Dixon et al., 2009). Folksonomies reflect an informal way for organizations to codify and categorize knowledge (Jackson, 2010). Along those lines, tags were noted as a common way to help organize the knowledge to facilitate future use (Andriole, 2010; Kimmerle et al., 2010). “The knowledge worker adds social tags to found resources, helping them – and others – to find the resource in the future.” (Jackson & Klobas, 2010, p. 6). Another useful function mentioned was automated recommenders, which use AI to examine past use and to search data to provide recommended articles and knowledge (Di Iorio & Rossi, 2018; Durao & Dolog, 2014). Essentially, collaborative technologies afford organizations access to stored knowledge through a host of capabilities that make it easier to locate information.

In addition to tagging and folksonomies, a few of the high-quality articles discussed the importance of the affordance of *channels*. Channels are a differentiated space for discussing

various projects, concepts, issues, or topics (Anders, 2016; Evans et al., 2015). Whereas email does not specifically contain channels, the choice of whom to carbon copy (cc) or blind carbon copy (bcc) simulates a channel, in that a certain group of people is targeted based on group members' roles and knowledge. However, the introduction of other collaborative technologies, especially IM, wikis and project management systems takes this a step further. Such systems enable the creation of groups and/or channels, which then focus a conversation on a particular project or topic, which can also foster complementary innovation (Schneckenberg et al., 2015). But the result is much different than in email, in that colleagues can leave or join the channels at various times according to their informational needs, yet the knowledge contained within the channel remains available and searchable to all in the channel (Dennerlein et al., 2016). In sum, channels are another technological feature that help organizations separate and categorize knowledge in ways that increase employees' access to expertise.

Finding Answers: Locating Experts. While many of the authors noted the importance of searching for information or knowledge, others focused on the ability to locate experts or “who knows what.” In this way, one of the affordances of collaborative technologies is connectivity to expertise. Even though the quality of content in a knowledge base can be lacking, the ability to locate experts can compensate (Durao & Dolog, 2014). Several authors noted how some employees use the knowledge base to locate an expert to contact directly (Alqahtani, 2017; Breunig, 2016; Durao & Dolog, 2014; Jarrahi & Sawyer, 2013; Krumova & Milanezi, 2014). It is also possible to locate topic experts via knowledge profiles, meta data, and metasearch (Brichni et al., 2014; Dal Mas et al., 2018; Jackson & Klobas, 2010; Schneckenberg et al., 2015) and for managers to recognize expertise in employees for selection for future projects (Archer-

Brown & Kietzmann, 2018; Stocker et al., 2012). As a result, the affordance of being able to locate expertise was found to be important for collaborative technologies.

Further examples of human connection facilitated by collaborative technologies involve signaling for support and clinical diagnoses. One important affordance noted as “one of the best uses” by Schneckenberg et al. (2015) was the “function signaling the need for urgent support, which is the capacity of the system to rapidly connect knowledge seekers and knowledge holders for joint problem-solving” (p. 363). This is achieved through posting to microblogging channels to specific networks where the expertise might be located. Similarly, in the health care sector, Pimmer et al. (2018) found that IM could facilitate clinical decision-making and joint diagnoses to address patient-related issues, particularly for patients in remote areas. Thus, the ability to flag, signal, or notify other people in order to solve problems or collaborate across geographical distances is notable.

Access to Knowledge. Access to knowledge is at the heart of organizational knowledge management. Many organizations have the long-term goal of capturing and aggregating knowledge that is reliable and usable by anyone in the company (Hemsley & Mason, 2013; Jackson & Klobas, 2010; Stocker et al., 2012). The captured knowledge, whether tacit or codified (Maity, 2019), whether via wiki (Hasan & Pfaff, 2012; Jackson, 2010) or IM (Pimmer et al., 2018) needs to be easily and universally accessible and scalable (Teo et al., 2011). Information should flow freely (Jackson, 2010; Teo et al., 2011), be accessible and modifiable (Stocker et al., 2012) and extendable (Jackson, 2010). Individual knowledge can also potentially be converted into collective organizational knowledge through Artificial Intelligence (AI), data mining or intelligent assistants (Maity, 2019). Thus, it is the access and free flow of information among an organization’s members that facilitates knowledge management first and foremost.

A few authors discussed access in terms of Transactive Memory Systems (TMS), which are “human systems which extend the knowledge and cognitive capabilities of individuals and enable couples and groups to access knowledge across a whole system of relationships” (Jackson & Klobas, 2010, p. 3). Through continuous revision, or shaping, of the knowledge in a wiki or within social media, a TMS “promotes knowledge reuse through improved knowledge integration” (Majchrzak et al., 2013a, p. 455) which can facilitate access to expert knowledge when it is needed (Jackson & Klobas, 2010). Social media, as part of a TMS, can also extend knowledge and facilitate access across groups. Ali et al. (2020) found that social media use has a significant effect on absorptive capacity, and a TMS has a highly significant effect on potential absorptive capacity, which relates to the organization’s capacity for innovation. Through the means of a TMS, organizations can move from individual to group knowledge, strengthening their knowledge and innovative capacity through social ties and group access.

Removing barriers to access and enhancing frequency of use are key to unlocking the benefits of collaborative technologies for knowledge management. Organizational barriers are of more importance than technical barriers (Bolisani & Scarso, 2016) since typically the technology is capable of being completely open, but organizational policies and restrictions may limit access. Menolli et al., (2015) noted that companies with no access restrictions were found to more rapidly add content and more frequently update it, and that “restrictions on access to the knowledge repository influence the frequency with which employees enter, update or consult content, and the way that the content is categorized influences the frequency with which it is used” (p. 301). Removing barriers and providing open access to knowledge and experts was found to be a significant affordance of collaborative technologies for organizational knowledge management.

Knowledge Sharing: Across Boundaries. A primary theme that emerged from the analysis of the inductive codes is that of knowledge crossing organizational and geographical boundaries. This occurs through social networks and media (Archer-Brown & Kietzmann, 2018; Hemsley & Mason, 2013), IM channels (Anders, 2016; Pimmer et al., 2018), accessibility and transparency (Bibbo et al., 2012; Breunig, 2016), knowledge sharing practices and collaboration methods (Krumova & Milanezi, 2014; Schneckenberg et al., 2015; Stocker et al., 2012) and a number of practices such as cross-training, un conferences and blogging to help break down silos (Teo et al., 2011). Indeed, collaborative technologies can facilitate the breaking down of organizational boundaries by making knowledge more accessible and available to members across these boundaries. However, this does require the organization to utilize the right tools, with the right goals, and in the right ways.

While there are boundaries and silos within organizations to be broken down, several authors also noted the affordance of social media to bring external knowledge from outside the organization in, or to foster knowledge flow in and out of the organization (Hemsley & Mason, 2013; Schneckenberg et al., 2015). For example, Ali et al. (2020) found that “social media usage at work and a transactive memory system significantly influence the absorptive capacity of a team to classify and assimilate external knowledge and efficiently transform and utilize it through smooth coordination among team members” (p. 7). Anders (2016) found that such external information flow could help clients empathize with the feasibility of requests and contribute feedback to the organization, while Jackson and Klobas (2010) similarly found advantages of knowledge sharing with business partners, customers, suppliers and vendors. Another benefit of connecting to external knowledge is that of learning and building from a workers’ colleague network (Jarrahi & Sawyer, 2013). For example, when colleagues connect

and share information and resources on Twitter or other related social media, this fosters the growth of internal knowledge from external knowledge sources. Yet, Bibbo et al. (2012) warned that some companies do not want proprietary information shared externally, so the benefits must be weighed against the risks, and organizations must consider which information is able to be shared externally versus which is proprietary and must not be shared.

Culture

A second primary finding is that organizational culture is deeply intertwined with affordances of collaborative technologies for knowledge management. Since affordances of a particular collaborative technology can vary from organization to organization, culture can be a factor that greatly affects what those affordances are, how pervasive and effective the knowledge management practices are and what the organizational outcomes are. Twelve of the included articles (26%) mentioned the importance of various aspects of organizational culture to foster knowledge management with collaborative technologies. These primary aspects include importance of managers/management support, transparency and continuance of use.

Knowledge Sharing Culture. An organization's culture is central to its knowledge sharing capability. Organizations can incentivize knowledge sharing behavior and foster innovation through openness, collaboration, semantic search, sharing tacit knowledge and providing access to explicit knowledge (Hasan & Pfaff, 2012; Schneckenberg et al., 2015; Stocker et al., 2012). Pillet and Carillo (2016) posited that "the quicker individuals get into the habit of using collaborative tools, the faster an organization will establish a collaborative culture and will in turn benefit from the development of knowledge sharing behaviors among employees" (p. 123). Thus, an organization's culture needs to encourage and demand the exchange of knowledge in a cooperative setting (Dal Mas et al., 2018; Hasan & Pfaff, 2012) and

information needs to flow freely, but this may necessitate large-scale changes in employee behaviors and practices which may have attached risks and uncertainties (Teo et al., 2011). These are some of the ways organizations have worked toward a productive knowledge sharing culture.

It is no small feat to change corporate culture. It may require a paradigm shift and establishment of new work behaviors to replace those that have been set in stone for many decades (Pillet & Carillo, 2016) and are very difficult to change (Jackson, 2010). Hierarchical and traditional workplace cultures typically experience skepticism toward new technologies such as a wiki (Hasan & Pfaff, 2012), and such climates benefit from flexibility, tolerance to error and innovativeness (Bolisani & Scarso, 2016). Yet the concept of organizational culture is also changing organically, as workers are no longer only immersed in their own organizational culture during the workday. By being connected to colleagues across the country and planet through social media and collaborative technologies, employees can learn about and even experience other organizational cultures through sharing of resources and online discussions. Knowledge management systems should have both work-related and social-related functions (Nisar et al., 2019). Social media makes it possible for workers to access their own and other networks and cultures by connecting and sharing knowledge across work period time boundaries and across businesses and sectors (Hemsley & Mason, 2013). Therefore, while an organization can strive to create and maintain a knowledge sharing culture, employees may also be influenced by colleagues and cultures in other organizations, and both elements can foster change.

Importance of Managers and Leadership. Fourteen of the 46 articles discuss the importance and support of management for collaborative technology use in knowledge management. First and foremost, the consensus is that managers, as primary drivers of cultural

change, need to be explicitly and deeply involved with adoption, implementation, and the on-going cultural shift toward collaborative culture (Alqahtani, 2017; Dal Mas et al., 2018; Hasan & Pfaff, 2012; Jackson, 2010; Skok et al., 2013; Teo et al., 2011). Managers can implement incentives, rewards and recognition for contributions (Beck, 2015; Hasan & Pfaff, 2012); help employees develop usage habits (Pillet & Carillo, 2016); and lead by example through their use of and promotion of the tools (Alqahtani, 2017; Bibbo et al., 2012) and of soft skills to encourage cooperation (as opposed to authoritative enforcements) (Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016). Managers are in the position to help employees break old habits and establish new ones, but this requires continuous effort to manage change (Pillet & Carillo, 2016). Indeed, managers play a central and important role for KM.

In addition to managers, buy-in from an organization's leadership is also important. Leaders can facilitate success by fostering buy-in from stakeholders (Ajjan et al, 2014; Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016), promoting trust and valuing contributions (Dal Mas et al., 2018), championing the initiative and fostering a climate conducive to collaboration and experimentation (Bolisani & Scarso, 2016), communicating the need for knowledge sharing initiatives, and establishing metrics to gauge success (Teo et al., 2011).

Transparency. Transparency was the second most coded construct, with 13 of the 46 articles addressing its relation to collaborative technologies in knowledge management. A common theme undergirding the value of transparency to the organization is the network and community that are formed as knowledge transcends organizational boundaries (Archer-Brown & Kietzmann, 2018; Breunig, 2016) and is made accessible to all members of an organization for conversations and problem solving. This transparency can foster robust knowledge management that can help organizations grow in size and expand in new markets (Maity, 2019), generate

ideas or spark innovation (Anders, 2016; Schneckenberg et al., 2015), increase the visibility of initiatives (Skok et al., 2013) or focus creative potential and design new products (Stocker et al., 2012). Transparency is a central construct for organizations to foster KM.

Wikis were specifically noted for their ability to increase transparency (Breunig, 2015; Stocker et al., 2012), especially above and beyond email, since wiki content can be either openly available or easily shared with others in a way that is difficult to accomplish with email. Breunig (2016) elaborated:

“many e-mail exchanges excluded people who might benefit from their content, as engineers recorded discussions by storing relevant e-mails and later forwarding them to others facing similar challenges. However, old e-mail chains can be outdated, and the quality of their content is more difficult to assure when the exchange was not transparent and open. Part of the motivation behind the wiki initiative was to avoid these e-mail loops, but it also had several other effects concerning knowledge sharing and interaction among globally distributed colleagues” (p. 257).

Anders (2016) found a similar effect for IM: email impedes knowledge sharing and locating information in a timely fashion. Further, Anders noted:

“important organizational information is often hidden in individual users’ inboxes and that group conversations often include too many or too few participants. Users also described e-mail as an inefficient medium for the type of brief, synchronous messages that characterize routine team communication. E-mail messaging structures were argued to add extraneous information with group discussions in e-mail chains becoming unwieldy and difficult to follow. These factors exacerbate the challenges of collaboration, especially for new team members who do not have access to the original messages” (p. 241).

In these ways, wikis and IM systems can add a level of transparency that facilitates knowledge sharing.

Blockchain technology was also mentioned in relation to transparency. Ilbiz and Durst (2019) posited that shared blockchain ledgers can both provide transparency and protect data from untrusted shareholders or data corruption. This can contribute to a competitive edge and boost trust between companies and customers, since the provenance of purchased products is

encapsulated in the ledgers. Yet, they also acknowledge an associated risk of “revealing all private transaction information to the blockchain network” (p. 34). It is still somewhat early in the blockchain technology lifecycle, so it is expected that more evidence regarding this technology will be forthcoming in future years.

Adoption/Implementation. In addition to the importance of management, leadership and transparency, this systematic review revealed several aspects of organizational culture relating to the adoption and/or implementation of various collaborative technologies as being important for KM. These findings point to the importance of adopting and implementing KM systems, as well as fostering their continued use so that KM systems are ingrained in the organizational culture.

Getting Started: Building from Nothing. Many organizations struggle with implementation and how to get started using collaborative technologies for knowledge management. The evidence points to some essential practical steps that organizations can use to foster smooth adoption and implementation. First, an organization-wide audit and comprehensive strategy and roadmap for implementation can create a positive impact (Skok et al., 2013). Further, in an empirical study on the implementation of wikis for knowledge diffusion across several sectors, Alqahtani (2017) recommended that the technology is aligned with core business objectives and its use is embedded within normal business processes; wiki champions and management lead by example, commonly using the tools; and easy to use tools are selected for knowledge sharing self-efficacy. Similarly, Stocker et al. (2012) found that communicating a business-oriented goal as it relates to the initial situation and the desired outcomes and benefits of the wiki are advantageous. Finally, it is important to align the tools’ intention and purpose (Ajjan et al., 2014; Dennerlein et al., 2016). Thus, one of the first and most important steps for

adoption is for organizations to conduct a self-study and to fully understand and communicate its situation, goals, and strategy to all stakeholders.

Initiation of a knowledge management system is also an area that benefits from observing the evidence. Stocker et al. (2012) found that employees only see the value of wikis after using them extensively, which can be a hurdle in the early phases of initiation. This can be addressed by constructing an initial knowledge base and infrastructure with a critical mass of information before launching to the whole organization (Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016). Some employees may begin using the collaborative technology, but then go back to doing things their old way, so it is important to gain consensus about usage habits and tools usage to encourage widespread adoption (Evans, 2015). The way organizations initiate a KM system can have a large effect on the people and processes, so it must be undertaken with care.

Continuance of Use: Keeping Knowledge Updated. Ten of the included studies described continuance of use as an important factor of successful adoption. If the knowledge is not kept up to date, it will eventually become useless; it needs to be updated and maintained over time (Jackson, 2010; Stocker et al., 2012) Organizations that newly adopt and implement collaborative technologies (as opposed to using them from the very beginnings of the company) face challenges related to getting started, changing employee habit patterns, company culture related to communication and collaboration, keeping knowledge and information up to date, and “attention competition.” Jarrahi and Sawyer (2013) found that “social technologies ‘compete’ with one another for the attention of the worker. That is, knowledge workers constantly compare the functional capabilities of available social technologies and perceive one more effective than others in supporting knowledge practices” (p. 129).

Another dimension of attention is that of a barrage of notifications and messages arriving via various technologies, which can be distracting or impinge on work-life balance as employees engage while on vacation or after work hours (Anders, 2016). Therefore, as companies implement KM systems, it is important to have the big picture and long term in mind in order to create an environment that is conducive to continued use.

Findings on the possible impacts of information overload were mixed in the included studies. Ali et al. (2012) found that the availability of more information led to more access to that information, and that “employees are not relying on withdrawing strategy to deal with information overload” (p. 504). Conversely, and in subsequent studies, Anders (2016) noted that the volume of information can be overwhelming to employees, and Schneckenberg et al. (2015) agreed, noting overload as a challenge that can threaten innovation. Thus, it is apparent that continuance of use could be affected by information overload.

Other methods for fostering continuance of use were noted. Pillet and Carillo (2016) outlined the importance of habit formation and the inclusion of features that reinforce continuance of use, such as gamification or reward features. Beck et al. (2015) further recommended gamification as a means to make knowledge integration (KI) and creation enjoyable, motivate employees through incentives or rewards or advance their reputations. They suggested that rewards are “the single most important factor for encouraging KI behavior. Creating an environment in which people feel a strong sense of commitment to the shared knowledge repository, and designing a system that requires little effort to reorganize and add to knowledge created by others, will also promote KI behavior” (p. 415). Iglesias-Pradas et al. (2015) recommended an incentive structure that recognizes the value of individual contributions. Some authors used competition as a motivator, engaging employees to post blogs and then vote

for the top posts (Teo et al., 2011). On the other hand, Bolisani and Scarso (2016) posited that rewards were not needed because the wiki was simply helpful in employees' daily work, so they used the system naturally. Each organization may need to come up with its own best formula for fostering continued use.

Ease of Use. Eleven authors noted the importance of ease of use to foster knowledge management through collaborative technologies. Several authors specifically noted wikis for their relative ease of use for adoption and implementation (Alqahtani, 2017; Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016; Bibbo et al., 2012; Jackson, 2010). The wiki should be user-friendly and intuitive (Alqahtani, 2017; Bolisani & Scarso, 2016) and can be effortless and instantaneous (Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016). Some authors noted that the wiki needed to be more intuitive and continuously assessed for improvement (Bolisani & Scarso, 2016). As such, Stocker et al. (2012) warns against some wiki systems that can be overly complex, challenging and obscure, which can cloud any value added by the wiki. IM was also noted by multiple authors for its ease of use, perhaps due to its speed of communication (Anders, 2016; Pimmer et al., 2018). And IM ease of use was noted as contributing to continuance of use (Ajjan et al., 2014). Thus, ease of use is important for the entire lifecycle of any chosen collaborative technology tool.

Ease of use was also linked through the evidence to employee habits. Pillet and Carillo (2016) found a significant path between perceived ease of use and habit. One dimension of ease is authentication, which could be a barrier if not integrated with the suite of tools in use (Bibbo et al., 2012; Skok et al., 2013). For example, if employees are expected to log into a tool regularly but have to maintain a separate authentication identity (as opposed to single sign-on) this could be a barrier to ease of use and usage habits.

Interesting Use Cases

A few authors noted interesting uses or outlier outcomes that may not have been duplicated by other studies, but which are worth mentioning. In terms of acceptance and use of wikis, one study found that a certain amount of anonymity was conducive to lowering users' social anxiety (Iglesias-Pradas et al., 2015). This goes somewhat against the idea of transparency, but some organizations at certain stages may find that certain topics or systems may benefit at some stages of their KM processes from anonymity. Menolli et al. (2015) also found that wikis and collaborative writing tools such as Google Docs are best at promoting double loop learning, where employees question the values, beliefs and policies to better understand the effects of processes of the organization. Companies wishing to get to this level of engagement may want to focus on incorporating such tools and encouraging this type of participation.

Finally, Hemsley and Mason (2013) discussed social media tools and how they blur the lines between "at work" and "at home" during non-working hours, thus immersing employees in organizational culture outside the workplace. Traditionally, and prior to the information expansion of the internet, employees were mostly immersed in their own organizational culture only while at work. But by using social media, this can also blend with other organizational cultures. For example, imagine an employee who finds an interesting and relevant work-related article and posts it to their LinkedIn or Facebook network, which contains both colleagues from within and outside their organization. This may lead to discussion, further resource-sharing and learning which blends multiple organizational cultures in conversation. It can also mean that employees reach out for just-in-time problem solving, resources and knowledge beyond their own company knowledge base using social media. For this reason, Hemsley and Mason (2013)

recommend against corporate blocking of social media sites, which they found could inhibit innovation and create barriers to retaining younger employees. The judicious allowance of anonymity, collaborative writing and social media technologies should be explored by organizations, depending on their goals, objectives and culture.

Organizational Outcomes

Across the included articles in this systematic review, a number of organizational outcomes were found to be prevalent among the analytic codes. Continuous improvement was a noted outcome among 11 of the articles, while eight mentioned the enhancement of organizational productivity and the social network. Innovation was also mentioned by seven authors as an organizational outcome. Finally, a handful of authors mentioned the enhancement of efficiency, connectivity and competitive advantage for the organization in relation to KM initiatives. Notably, competitive advantage was not found to be as common an outcome as expected. Figure 11 displays these outcomes in a conceptual model that also portrays the primary codes and themes from the included articles as a result of the thematic analysis.

Figure 11

Conceptual Map of Study Findings

The findings of this study of CTs that include wikis, IM, groupware, web 2.0 and social media applications, AI and blockchain and how organizations can utilize them for KM revealed two major categories as seen in Figure 11: affordances and culture. Each of these categories included a number of themes that connect the CTs to the organization’s KM systems. As noted in the literature, several notable organizational outcomes resulted from the usage of CTs. Reflecting on the theoretical underpinnings and model noted in Chapter 2 (see Figure 3), these findings have both congruency and incongruency with the organizational outcomes. While the finding that many studies mention innovation and competitive advantage as organizational outcomes of using CTs was expected, this study found more reports of continuous improvement, enhanced productivity, social network and innovation, with only a small number of studies noting competitive advantage as an outcome.

Chapter Summary

In summary, this chapter discussed the findings of this qualitative systematic review and analysis of the inductive thematic coding of 46 scholarly articles regarding how organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management. The body of evidence pointed to two major categories: affordances (access to knowledge, knowledge sharing across boundaries and searchability) and cultural aspects (knowledge sharing culture, transparency, importance of managers and adoption/implementation and ease of use) as key factors. This leads to several conclusions and recommendations, presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 5: Conclusions and Implications

Through a rigorous and transparent methodology, this scholarly systematic review of evidence on how organizations utilize collaborative technologies (CTs) for knowledge management (KM) provides insight into several of the primary mechanisms that foster success. With the specific findings from the articles reported in the previous chapter, this chapter provides conclusions and describes managerial implications that may be applicable to practitioners. Based on the findings from the systematic review, this chapter posits some practical steps for practitioners.

Answer to the Research Question

The research question guiding this dissertation was: *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* Based on this systematic review of the evidence collected through qualitative analysis, the two predominant thematic categories of affordances and organizational culture provide insight as to how organizations implement and benefit from collaborative technologies. Affordances found to be of importance included: access to knowledge and expertise, searchability and knowledge sharing across organizational boundaries. Aspects of organizational culture found to be most significant included: the building of a culture conducive to knowledge sharing, the importance of managers and leadership, transparency and ease of use. Together, these affordances and aspects of organizational culture formulate the core findings of this research and provide the basis for the implications to management.

Affordances: Management Implications

It behooves managers to help guide the selection of CTs based on the overall goals, objectives and culture of the organization. Affordances by their nature can differ from

technology to technology and organization to organization. From the included studies and organizations, this study revealed that the affordances of searchability, finding useful information, building a knowledge base, providing access to knowledge, problem solving, locating experts, finding “who knows what,” tagging and channels as being important for collaborative technologies to affect organizational knowledge management. Managers could use this list of affordances as a starting point for assessing proposed or already in place technology tools, to see how well they align with the organization’s KM goals. Alternatively, managers can use this as a jumping off point to study and identify what their most important affordances are.

Access and Breaking Down Silos

With its central importance to organizational KM, managers need to prioritize easy and open access to the tools and knowledge across the organization. Managers should work with IT leadership to ensure authentication to the CTs and/or KM system are tied into the enterprise with single sign-on. The tools must work across all the various devices and systems in use in the organization. For example, using an IM tool such as Slack or Microsoft Teams will help ensure that employees can use them on all various devices, whereas other tools may be specific to only one operating system and will not work across devices. It is also best to utilize the same tools across the organization - as opposed to having so much decentralization that some business units or workgroups use different tools than others within the same organization. If the central business department is using Slack and Google Drive, it makes it much more difficult to share across silos if the marketing department is using Microsoft Teams and Dropbox. Building buy-in and consensus to use the same tools in similar ways across the enterprise will enable more sharing across boundaries. Managers can help build this consensus by being an example, using

the CTs to communicate and collaborate with all other employees and continuously rewarding efforts to create and maintain organizational knowledge.

Searchability

Using CTs and KM systems can benefit many organizations through the affordance of searchability. It stands to reason that moving from paper to computers and then to internet-based knowledge storage has increased the speed and reliability of searching for knowledge when it is needed. The technical capability to enter a search string and be able to locate documents, chats, knowledge base entries, tickets, code or any form of knowledge, has made this invaluable to many organizations. But knowledge is only searchable if it is open and accessible to those who need it and the knowledge has been entered/included on record. So, this requires managers to incentivize sharing of knowledge using tools that are more open (IM, wiki, cloud-based collaborative file storage) versus those that are more closed (email, telephone, local file storage). Further, managers should incentivize employees to regularly and routinely add to and update the knowledge base or KM systems. Having up-to-date information that is tagged in channels and/or enhanced with metadata and semantic taxonomies will help ensure that data is searchable.

Most recently, organizations are investing in technology solutions that help ensure knowledge searchability through AI-based intelligent search, data mining, knowledge graphs, aggregation, automated processes, dashboards, chatbots and other sophisticated means of helping employees find the knowledge they are seeking. These AI-based systems can facilitate the combining of information from multiple knowledge bases or systems, as well as organizing and tagging of knowledge for later retrieval. Implementing AI systems for KM will require organizations to prioritize KM, invest in KM leadership and support infrastructure, as well as

systematically investigate and deploy AI tools with an eye on continuous development and improvement.

Knowledge Sharing (KS) Culture: Management Implications

One of the key findings of this study is that the culture of an organization can lead to significant differences in how that company strategizes, organizes, implements, supports and benefits from the affordances of CTs for KM. At the center of an organizational culture are managers and leadership. As key drivers of culture, here are some things managers can do to foster success with knowledge management:

1. Work with Human Resources to establish job descriptions, interview questions and appraisal criteria for KM. All of these can set expectations for employees to routinely and regularly create, share and update knowledge with co-workers and to use the various tools the organization has established.
2. Be an exemplar in using the collaborative technologies and embedding them into daily work practices, to help the entire organization normalize KS habits. In other words, don't use email all the time but expect employees to use IM. Managers need to lead by example and use soft skills to encourage participation.
3. Consider incentivizing and/or rewarding employees as the organization meets established metrics for new knowledge contributions, keeping the knowledge base up-to-date, and using the collected knowledge for projects or problem-solving.

Transparency

Managers need to establish transparency by leading by example and using transparent practices. Establish guidelines for which communications should be more open versus less open, which tools to use for certain types of communication and how to ensure that knowledge can be

accessed by anyone who needs it. This may require re-thinking or re-working the infrastructure of a knowledge base so that by default all workgroups have access to most knowledge and only certain types of information are closed to smaller groups. Keep in mind that when an organization opens knowledge beyond the normal workgroup boundaries, it can benefit multiple workgroups that overlap. Scholars have recently further developed the conceptualization surrounding transparency - and its relationship to the visibility of knowledge through the development of an empirically based Information Visibility Scale (ter Hoeven et al., 2019). Using such a scale will enable organizations to examine the effective dimensions of visibility as it relates to transparency in the organization. There are long and short versions of the scale, which ask the organization to answer questions regarding its information sharing practices. Organizations can use this scale to help focus on the areas of keeping records of information for critical decisions; documenting relevant and significant issues the organization faces; sharing information that has societal benefits, when it is customary and social responsible to do so; making sure that pertinent information can be easily accessed and providing information with enough background to be fully understood in a systematic way (ter Hoeven et al., 2019, p. 23).

Adoption/Implementation

As managers move toward adoption and implementation of various CTs for KM, they should keep the following in mind:

1. Build consensus across the enterprise based on a shared vision of an organizational learning culture with key principles of open sharing, transparency and collaboration.
2. Ensure adopted tools are aligned with core business objectives, vision, mission and key principles.

3. Foster continuance of use through modeling, building KM practices into daily routines, and incentivizing and rewarding employees who post new and updated knowledge as well as those who utilize and build upon the knowledge base.

Aside from the many scholarly peer-reviewed journals that provide access to rigorous research, a number of further useful resources can be utilized by practitioners to help companies navigate KM and CT implementation processes through benchmarking and guides. The American Productivity & Quality Center (APQC) is a membership-based organization that calls itself the “world’s foremost authority in benchmarking, best practices, process and performance improvement, and knowledge management (KM)” and which has a resource library on its website that provides a number of timely and useful publications in this area (APQC, 2020). Among these resources is one of the several published models that exist for measuring levels of organizational KM maturity. In addition, *KM World* is a magazine resource that provides case studies, trends analysis, webinars, and access to many cutting edge companies and technologies in the KM realm, and produces the *KM World Connect* conference (KMWorld, 2020). Practitioners can use these resources to connect with some of the latest news and trends as well as other organizations and leaders in the realm of KM.

Limitations of the Study

While this dissertation was completed under the expert guidance of faculty mentors, Dr. Denise Breckon and Dr. Marcia Bouchard, the majority of the research was conducted solely by the researcher. Appraisal, coding and thematic synthesis of included papers, for example, were completed by the author, so there is no measurement of validity across multiple reviewers. Yet the researcher did use the same criteria across all included articles, so the appraisal and coding are consistent according to this singular point of view.

Although new studies are released every month, the timing and process of this dissertation did not allow for the inclusion of articles published after April 2020 to be included in the systematic review. While this review covers a large number of different types of organizations, industries and geographical work contexts, generalizability may be limited beyond the 46 included work environments.

There is a limitation associated with the global pandemic of 2020, since it was not possible to retrieve physical books from the UMGC library during the majority of the year.

Areas for Future Research

There are several areas that this dissertation either did not explore or only briefly touched on that would benefit from future research. First, while this study cast a wide net, some industries may benefit from systematic reviews that are particular to their context, sector or industry which synthesize and illuminate how businesses or organizations similar to theirs can best benefit from CTs and KM. Next, with the noted importance of continuance of use and engagement, one area that was briefly mentioned which would benefit from further exploration is gamification and its potential influence on engagement and continuity. A randomized control or longitudinal study of employee engagement and longevity of use with gamified KM systems and/or CTs would be helpful to this area of scholarship. Third, while hordes of organizations have moved toward the use of IM systems like Slack and Microsoft Teams, with the result of moving much more communication and knowledge out of email and into more transparent access areas, the problem of searchability and ability to locate correct and useful knowledge when it is needed may continue to grow. While AI promises to help with that issue through tagging, recommender systems and chatbots, more direct empirical studies providing evidence of a positive causal relationship to locating knowledge are needed. And with the barrage of AI-

infused technologies currently flooding the KM arena, more study will be necessary to understand the benefits, challenges, costs and return on investment of AI-based systems to the KM enterprise. Finally, blockchain technology was only mentioned specifically by one included study (Ilbiz & Durst, 2019). Further study of its usefulness for KM will provide valuable future research.

COVID19 and Global Virtual Telework

A large portion of this dissertation was conducted during the 2020 global COVID19 pandemic, which brought a massive global telework experiment to the surface. Telework and virtual teams amplify the need for and usage of quality KS practices, CTs and overall KM that are independent of geographical and temporal dispersion. While only a small segment of the included studies in this dissertation were specific to virtual teams, future research on the efficacy of specific tools, techniques and strategies specific to workgroups who cannot meet, collaborate or communicate in a collocated work environment will be beneficial. One of the great advantages of CTs is that they typically can be used similarly from any internet-connected location, so they are telework-friendly. In addition, many organizations were jolted into implementing, using and supporting CTs that they weren't using before. For example, some institutions that weren't regularly using Microsoft Teams and Zoom videoconferencing were suddenly thrust into a position where everyone was expected to use these CTs for communication and collaboration. While hemorrhaging revenue due to the global pandemic, many companies reaped the benefit of reduced costs for transportation and accommodations for business travel, discovering that they could continue their work successfully at a distance using CTs. It is possible there will be an unintended collateral effect when they realize that more of

their organizational knowledge is actually stored, shared and retrievable in these CTs, and this may lead to a new paradigm in KM.

Emerging Technologies and the Future of Work

In addition to the technologies mentioned in this dissertation, there are a number of emerging tools and concepts not explored that are anticipated to have a greater impact on the post-COVID-19 workforce and in relation to the “Future of Work” (FOW) concept. The FOW is envisioned to be one of increasing automation, digital transformation, flexible work and rapid retraining/reskilling of the workforce (Horii & Sakurai, 2020). This retraining ties in with increasing use of AI as well as a mindset shift toward continuous learning that requires organizations to be agile and have strong skills-based learning, development and training initiatives (Bughin et al., 2020a; OECD, 2020). Increasing digitization of the workforce, coupled with the massive rapid changes from the global pandemic are also driving the FOW to include virtual worlds, Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) for simulations, new forms of communication and collaboration, meetings, learning and training and even to enable equity in the workplace (Cook & Kuczer, 2020). With the growth of robotics in conjunction with AI and the Internet of Things (IoT), people will increasingly be working side-by-side with machines and other people, with technology having significant potential to improve human well-being (Bughin et al., 2020b). An increased need and emphasis on learning and development will continue to drive the need for technology such as the Experience API (xAPI) that helps organizations track and analyze all the various ways employees learn and experience new information and training (PlayerLync, 2017). Such “Smart Learning Environments” (Hoel & Mason, 2018) and technologies are connecting KM with learning and development business units in ways that will foster organizational change to meet changing business needs. As corporate and organizational

cultures shift, tools that help decision-making and related data visualization like Loomio.org and Atlassian Jira will continue to allow organizations to update work methods and move valuable communication out of email and into more transparent spaces. In these ways, and through these technologies, a business transformation toward “Industry 4.0” is ushering in radical innovation (Kohnová et al., 2019). Such radical innovation and rapid change are defining the FOW as we know it.

Final Summary and Conclusion

In summary, this dissertation employed a systematic review to answer the research question, *How do organizations leverage collaborative technologies for knowledge management?* With baby boomers retiring and new generations entering the workplace, a workforce that is increasingly distributed (especially now, in 2020, during the worldwide COVID19 pandemic), and an economy that is increasingly dependent upon knowledge as its primary form of capital, the management and sharing of knowledge to mitigate knowledge loss and foster knowledge retention is paramount. This dissertation informs the field of KM through its synthesis of the best available evidence to answer the research question.

By analyzing and synthesizing findings from 46 scholarly articles from multiple organizational contexts and locations on every continent, this study contributes to the growing body of KM literature by highlighting common mechanisms across contexts that organizations have found useful for implementation, adoption and successful utilization of CTs for strategic KM. Based on the thematic synthesis of appraised and coded evidence, this dissertation shines a light on several aspects of affordances and organizational culture that scholars and practitioners can utilize in their decision-making related to CTs and KM.

The systematic review included a scoping literature review and description of the methodology that included a comprehensive search strategy, screening, vetting and application of inclusion/exclusion criteria, a rigorous process of appraisal for all 46 included articles, inductive thematic coding of all included article findings, and a synthesis of the resultant coding analysis. This review resulted in two primary categories of mechanisms for CTs to foster KM: affordances and organizational culture. The study provided comprehensive findings from the synthesis of 46 studies as well as recommendations for managers and leaders looking to employ KM strategies via CTs that may enhance their organization's efficiency, productivity, innovative capabilities and ultimately, longevity. The researcher recommends that managers facilitate the implementation, adoption and continuity of use of CTs through alignment with the organization's mission, vision and culture, through careful selection of tools that foster transparency across organizational boundaries, and by fostering an organizational culture of knowledge sharing.

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Appendix A

Table A1

Article Appraisal

Article Titles of article w/ authors	Transparency: Open to outside scrutiny, limitations presented, bias clear	Accuracy: Methodology	Weight of Evidence			Propriety: Stakeholders	Accessibility: Useful for reader/easy to understand/ sources used	Specificity: Research meets standards associated with this type of research	Average: Highest Score 3; Lowest Score 1.14
			Purposivity: Keywords of phrase: knowledge retention, management, transfer, storage, sharing;	Utility (Findings): Do the findings answer research question/the findings seem reasonable based on the methodological approach used?					
Scoring System : 1- Weak, 2- Mid, 3 -High. The scores represent the usefulness towards Locus and the weight of evidence provided.									
Ajjan 2012	1	3	3	1	3	2	3	2.29	
Ajjan 2014	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
Ali 2012	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	2.29	
Ali 2020	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
Alqahtani 2017	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2.71	
Anders 2016	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	2.71	
Andriole 2010	2	3	1	2	1	2	2	1.86	
Archer-Brown 2018	2	2	3	3	2	1	2	2.14	
Argyris 2016	1	3	1	2	3	2	2	2	
Baek 2012	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2.57	
Beck 2015	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2.71	
Bibbo 2012	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2.29	
Bolisani 2016	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2.29	
Breunig 2016	3	3	2	2	3	2	3	2.57	
Brichni 2014	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1.57	
Choy 2018	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	2.14	
DalMas 2018	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	2.14	
Dennerlein 2016	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	1.57	
DiIorio 2018	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1.86	
Durao 2014	2	1	3	2	3	2	3	2.29	
Evans 2015	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	2.57	
Hasan 2012	2	2	1	2	3	2	2	2	
Hemsley 2013	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2.71	
Iglesias-Pradas 2015	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2.86	
Ilbiz 2019	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1.43	
Jackson 2010	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	2.57	
Jackson Klobas 2010	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1.57	
Jarrahi 2013	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2.86	
Khumalo 2019	2	s	1	2	2	2	2	1.86	
Kimmerle 2010	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	2	
Krumova 2014	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1.14	
Maity 2019	1	1	3	2	2	2	2	1.86	
Majchrzak 2013	2	2	1	1	3	2	2	1.86	
Menolli 2015	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2.57	
Ngoma 2013	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	2.71	
Nisar 2019	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	2.57	
Ou 2010	3	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	
Paschen 2019	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1.43	
Pillet 2016	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2.86	
Pimmer 2018	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1.86	
Schneckenberg 2015	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.86	
Skok 2013	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	1.57	
Stocker 2012	3	2	3	3	3	2	2	2.57	
Teo 2011	2	2	3	3	1	2	2	2.14	
Tyagi 2015	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1.29	
Zapp 2013	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1.43	

Appendix B

Table B1

Data Extraction Table

Study Identifier	Study Design	Sponsorship source	Study Type	Country	Setting
Ajjan et al, 2012	Empirical	Information Resources Management Journal	PRJ	USA	Organizations
Ajjan et al, 2014	Empirical	Behaviour & Information Technology	PRJ	USA	Organizations
Ali et al., 2012	Empirical	Int'l Journal of Medical Informatics	PRJ	New Zealand	Healthcare Organizations
Ali et al., 2020	Empirical	Technology in Society	PRJ	China	Software Development Companies
Alqahtani, 2017	Empirical	Aslib Journal of Information Management	PRJ	Saudi Arabia	Organizations
Anders, 2016	Empirical	International Journal of Business Communication	PRJ	Various	Various
Andriole, 2010	Empirical	Communications of the ACM	PRJ	USA	Various
Archer-Brown & Kietzmann, 2018	Theoretical Paper	Journal of Knowledge Management	PRJ	UK	N/A
Argyris & Ransbotham, 2016	Case Study	Journal of Information Technology	PRJ	USA	Organizations
Baek, 2012 - dissertation	Empirical	Dissertation	Diss.	USA	Various
Beck et al., 2015	Empirical	Journal of Business Economics	PRJ	Various	Financial services
Bibbo et al., 2012	Case Study	Journal of Information	PRJ	USA	Media Company

		Technology Teaching Cases			
Bolisani & Scarso, 2016	Empirical	Journal of Knowledge Management	PRJ	Italy	Company
Breunig, 2016	Case Study	The Learning Organization	PRJ	Norway	International knowledge-based service organization
Brichni et al., 2014	Case Study	Journal of Knowledge Management	PRJ	France	Manufacturing
Choy et al., 2018	Case Study	VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems	PRJ	Taiwan	Nursing Home
Dal Mas et al., 2018	Case Study	15th International Conference on Intellectual Capital Knowledge Management & Organisational Learning	CP	Switzerland	Organizations
Dennerlein et al., 2016	Case Study		CP	Austria	Various
Di Iorio & Rossi, 2018	Case Study	Information Sciences	PRJ	Italy	University
Durao & Dolog, 2014	Empirical	Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing	PRJ	Denmark	University
Evans et al., 2015	Empirical	International Journal of Advanced Corporate Learning	PRJ	UK	Students + Industry
Hasan & Pfaff, 2012	Case Study	Information Technology & People	PRJ	Australia	Various

Hemsley & Mason, 2013	Theoretical Paper	Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce	PRJ	USA	Organizations
Iglesias-Pradas et al., 2015	Empirical	Journal of Business Research	PRJ	Spain	Information Systems department of a large multinational industrial company based in Spain.
Ilbiz et al., 2019	Theoretical Paper	Journal of Innovation Management	PRJ	Various	Various
Jackson, 2010	Action Research	Industrial Management & Data Systems	PRJ	Australia	Supply Chain Business
Jackson & Klobas, 2010	Theoretical Paper	Bocconi University. Carlo F. Dondena Centre for Research on Social Dynamics, Milan, Italy	WP	Italy	University Research
Jarrahi & Sawyer, 2013	Empirical	Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce	PRJ	USA	Participants in the main study held knowledge-intensive roles in consulting firms; purposive sampling
Khumalo & Mearns, 2019	Empirical	South African Journal of Information Management	PRJ	South Africa	Retail business
Kimmerle et al., 2010	Theoretical Paper	Knowledge Management Research & Practice	PRJ	Germany	Organizations
Krumova & Milanezi, 2014	General report	KSI Transactions on KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY	PRJ	N/A	N/A
Maity, 2019	Empirical	Journal of Management	PRJ	India	Various HR

		Development			
Majchrzak et al., 2013a	Empirical	Mis Quarterly	PRJ	Various	Various
Menolli et al., 2015	Empirical	Information and Software Technology	PRJ	Brazil	Software Development Companies
Ngoma, 2013	Empirical	Capella University	Diss.	USA	N/A
Nisar et al., 2019	Empirical	Journal of Business Research	PRJ	UK	N/A
Ou et al., 2010	Empirical	Information Technology & People	PRJ	China	Business professionals
Paschen et al., 2019	Theoretical Paper	Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing	PRJ	N/A	B2B Marketing
Pillet & Carillo, 2016	Case Study	International Journal of Information Management	PRJ	France/Poland	KIF (Knowledge Intensive Firm)
Pimmer et al., 2018	Empirical	Knowledge Management & E-Learning: An International Journal	PRJ	Global	Global Health practitioners
Schneckenberg et al., 2015	Empirical	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	PRJ	France	Global Industrial Firm
Skok et al., 2013	Case Study	Knowledge and Process Management	PRJ	UK	Global Energy Consulting Group
Stocker, et al., 2012	Case Study	Computer Supported Cooperative Work	PRJ	Austria	Various companies
Teo et al., 2011	Case Study	MIS Quarterly Executive	PRJ	India	Corporate IT
Tyagi et al., 2015	Theoretical Paper	Proceedings of the 2015 Industrial and Systems	CP	USA	Design Business

		Engineering Research Conference			
Zapp, 2013	Theoretical Paper	8th CIRP Conference on Intelligent Computation in Manufacturing Engineering	CP	Germany	Manufacturing

Note. Study Types include: Peer Reviewed Journal (PRJ); Dissertation (Diss); Conference Proceeding (CP) and Working Paper (WP).

Appendix B

Table B2

Primary Collaborative Technology by Article/Year

Study	Primary Collaborative Technology		
		Iglesias-Pradas 2015	wiki
Ajjan 2012	web 2.0	Ilbiz 2019	blockchain
Ajjan 2014	IM	Jackson 2010	wiki
Ali 2012	web 2.0	Jackson & Klobas	
Ali 2020	social media	2010	web 2.0
Alqahtani 2017	wiki	Jarrahi 2013	social media
Anders 2016	IM	Khumalo 2019	Sharepoint
Andriole 2010	web 2.0	Kimmerle 2010	wiki
Archer-Brown 2018	social media	Krumova 2014	web 2.0
Argyris 2016	wiki	Maity 2019	AI
Baek 2012	IM	Majchrzak 2013	wiki
Beck 2015	wiki	Menolli 2015	web 2.0
Bibbo 2012	wiki	Ngoma 2013	web 2.0
Bolisani 2016	wiki	Nisar 2019	social media
Breunig 2016	wiki	Ou 2010	IM
Brichni 2014	wiki	Paschen 2019	AI
Choy 2018	AI	Pillet 2016	web 2.0
DalMas 2018	social media	Pimmer 2018	IM
Dennerlein 2016	IM	Schneckenberg 2015	web 2.0
DiIorio 2018	wiki	Skok 2013	Sharepoint
Durao 2014	wiki	Stocker 2012	wiki
Evans 2015	web 2.0	Teo 2011	web 2.0
Hasan 2012	wiki	Tyagi 2015	wiki
Hemsley 2013	social media	Zapp 2013	wiki

Appendix C

Figure C1

Codes Across Articles: Affordances

	o searchability	o find useful information	o knowledgebase	o access to knowledge	o problem solving	o across boundaries	o locate experts	o Who knows what	o engagement	o bring external knowledge in	Totals
Totals	17	12	12	11	11	11	9	8	7	6	
Ajjan 2012											0
Ajjan 2014											0
Ali 2012			X				X				2
Ali 2020										X	1
Alqahtani 2017											0
Anders 2016	X	X				X			X	X	5
Andriole 2010											0
Archer-Brown 2018					X	X	X				3
Argyris 2016			X								1
Baek 2012					X						1
Beck 2015			X								1
Bibbo 2012	X	X				X					3
Bolisani Scarso2016	X	X									2
Breunig 2016	X					X	X	X			4
Brichni 2014	X	X						X			3
Choy 2018											0
DalMas 2018						X		X	X		3
Dennerlein 2016	X										1
Dilorio 2018			X								1
Durao 2014	X	X			X		X		X		5
Evans 2015					X						1
Hasan 2012	X		X	X							3
Hensley 2013	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	8
Iglesias-Pradas 2015											0
Ilibiz 2019											0
Jackson 2010			X	X							2
Jackson Klobas 2010	X		X	X			X	X		X	6
Jarrahi 2013	X	X			X		X	X		X	6
Khumalo 2019	X		X					X			3
Kimmerle 2010											0
Krumova 2014					X	X					2
Maity 2019				X							1
Majchrzak 2013				X							1
Menolli 2015		X	X	X	X						4
Ngoma 2013											0
Nisar 2019											0
Ou 2010									X		1
Paschen 2019			X								1
Pillet 2016											0
Pimmer 2018		X		X	X	X					4
Schneckenberg 2015	X	X		X	X	X	X			X	7
Skok 2013									X		1
Stocker 2012	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			8
Teo 2011	X	X	X	X		X		X	X		7
Tyagi 2015	X										1
Zapp 2013	X										1
Totals	17	12	12	11	11	11	9	8	7	6	

Note: Columns indicate the most frequently coded constructs under the “Affordances” category

Appendix C

Figure C2

Codes Across Articles: Culture

	• importance of managers	• transparency	• continuence of use	• management support	• leadership importance	Totals
Totals	14	13	10	9	5	
Ajjan 2012			X			1
Ajjan 2014			X			1
Ali 2012						0
Ali 2020						0
Alqahtani 2017						0
Anders 2016		X				1
Andriole 2010						0
Archer-Brown 2018		X				1
Argyris 2016						0
Baek 2012	X				X	2
Beck 2015						0
Bibbo 2012	X			X	X	3
Bolisani Scarso2016	X	X	X			3
Breunig 2016	X	X		X		3
Brichni 2014						0
Choy 2018						0
DalMas 2018		X				1
Dennerlein 2016						0
Dilorio 2018						0
Durao 2014	X					1
Evans 2015			X			1
Hasan 2012	X			X		2
Hemsley 2013						0
Iglesias-Pradas 2015						0
Ilbiz 2019		X				1
Jackson 2010			X			1
Jackson Klobas 2010		X	X			2
Jarrahi 2013	X			X		2
Khumalo 2019						0
Kimmerle 2010	X			X		2
Krumova 2014	X					1
Maity 2019		X		X	X	3
Majchrzak 2013						0
Menolli 2015		X	X			2
Ngoma 2013						0
Nisar 2019						0
Ou 2010	X			X		2
Paschen 2019	X				X	2
Pillet 2016			X			1
Pimmer 2018	X		X	X		3
Schneckenberg 2015		X				1
Skok 2013		X				1
Stocker 2012	X	X	X	X	X	5
Teo 2011		X				1
Tyagi 2015	X					1
Zapp 2013						0
Totals	14	13	10	9	5	

Appendix C

Figure C3

Codes Across Articles: Affordances

Note: One green dot indicates coding from more than 50% high quality articles, two green dots indicates more than 75% high quality articles, one orange dot indicates more than 50% low quality articles.

Appendix C

Figure C4

Codes Across Articles: Adoption/Implementation/Culture

Note: One green dot indicates coding from more than 50% high quality articles, two green dots indicates more than 75% high quality articles, one orange dot indicates more than 50% low quality articles. Green codes indicate the most common codes across articles, followed by yellow and orange.